

D 3.2

Report on additional indicators of monitoring system

UnitelmaSapienza
Università degli Studi di Roma

Funded by
the European Union

www.star4bbs.eu
info@star4bbs.eu

@STAR4BBS

D 3.2

Report on additional indicators of monitoring system

DELIVERABLE TYPE

Report

MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERABLE

M15, 30/11/2023

WORK PACKAGE

WP 3

LEADER

USC

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

Public

AUTHORS

USC & TUB

Programme

HORIZON
EUROPE

Grant Agreement

101060588

Start

Sept.2022

Duration

36
Months

Contributors

NAME	ORGANISATION
Sara Lago Oliveira	USC
Ana Arias	USC
Ricardo Rebolledo Leiva	USC
María Teresa Moreira	USC
Nikola Matovic	TUB
Luana Ladu	TUB

Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
Tilman Denkler	BAM

Revision History

VERSION	ORGANISATION	REVIEWER	MODIFICATIONS
V1	21/11/2023	Luana Ladu & Nikola Matovic	General remarks, results improvement, editing
V2	27/11/2023	Tilman Denkler	General remarks, results improvement, editing
V3	29/11/2023	Sara Lago	Final draft

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Glossary.....	9
1 Introduction.....	12
2 Methodology.....	14
2.1 System level methodology.....	14
2.1.1 Preparation of a long list of SL elements.....	14
2.1.2 Comparing requirements of selected tools.....	15
2.1.3 Identification and selection of categories for the SL.....	16
2.1.4 Checking consistency with existing policies and ISEAL guidelines.....	16
2.1.5 Stakeholder input.....	17
2.1.6 Validation of selected principles, criteria and indicators.....	19
2.2 Content level methodology.....	19
2.2.1 Selection of certification schemes.....	20
2.2.2 Selection of monitoring systems.....	21
2.2.3 Data gathering, categorization and content analysis.....	22
2.2.4 Analysis of circularity indicators.....	26
2.2.5 Definition of indicators for the content level of the new monitoring system.....	28
3 Results from the analysis.....	29
3.1 System level.....	29
3.1.1 Selected system level characteristics.....	30
3.1.2 Categories of the System Level.....	31
3.1.2.1 Scheme Management.....	32
3.1.2.2 Standard Setting.....	32
3.1.2.3 Assurance.....	33
3.1.2.4 Traceability and claims.....	34
3.2 Results and trends from the certification schemes.....	35
3.2.1 Environmental pillar.....	36
3.2.2 Social pillar.....	40
3.2.3 Circularity pillar.....	44
3.2.4 Economic pillar.....	47
3.2.5 Sustainable governance pillar.....	48
3.2.6 Trends based on the typology of the requirement.....	49
3.3 Results and trends from the monitoring systems.....	54
3.3.1 Environmental pillar.....	55
3.3.2 Social pillar.....	58
3.3.3 Circularity pillar.....	60
3.3.4 Economic pillar.....	62

3.3.5 Sustainable governance pillar	63
3.4 Results from other sources	64
4 Final set of indicators	67
4.1 System level indicators	67
4.2 Content level indicators	67
5 Conclusions	68
6 Appendix	70
6.1 Selection of certification schemes	70
6.2 System Level Matrix	71
6.3 Content Level Matrix	71
7 References	72

Index of Tables

Table 1. List of selected certification schemes for in-depth content analysis	20
Table 2. List of selected monitoring systems for in-depth content analysis	21
Table 3. Summary of parameters used to categorize criteria, indicators and requirements	22
Table 4. Summary of pillars, key areas and subareas, as defined in D3.1	23
Table 5. Summary of additional pillars, key areas, subareas and associated definitions	25
Table 6. Initially identified 7 categories for the system level	30
Table 7. Categories and principles of the system level	31
Table 8. Preliminary list of circularity indicators	64
Table 9. Scoring of certification schemes for the final section	70

Index of Figures

Figure 1. Graphical representation of methodological approach for SL characteristics selection	15
Figure 2. Initially identified categories for the system level	16
Figure 3. Summary of the various indicators, criteria and requirements that will be referred to throughout this report. The certification schemes RSB, Better Biomass and the monitoring system FEAC are included as example. SCS: sustainable certification schemes; MS: monitoring system	29
Figure 4. Finally selected SL categories	30
Figure 5. a) distribution of pre-selected principles numbers among categories; b) distribution of criteria and requirements numbers per category	31
Figure 6. Distribution of requirements across pillars in analyzed certification schemes	35
Figure 7. Distribution of requirements across pillars per certification scheme	36
Figure 8. Distribution of requirements across environmental key areas in analyzed certification schemes	37

Figure 9. Distribution of requirements across environmental subareas per key area in analyzed certification schemes (only those key areas that have more than one subarea are represented)..... 38

Figure 10. Distribution of requirements across environmental key areas per certification scheme..... 39

Figure 11. Distribution of requirements across social key areas in analyzed certification schemes. 40

Figure 12. Distribution of requirements across social key areas in each certification scheme..... 41

Figure 13. Distribution of requirements across social subareas per key areas in analyzed certification schemes..... 42

Figure 14. Distribution of requirements across circularity key areas in each certification scheme..... 44

Figure 15. Distribution of requirements across circularity key areas in analyzed certification schemes..... 46

Figure 16. Number of circularity requirements per circularity subarea and per key area in analyzed certification schemes..... 46

Figure 17. Distribution of requirements across economic key areas in each certification scheme..... 47

Figure 18. Distribution of requirements across economic key areas in analyzed certification schemes..... 47

Figure 19. Distribution of requirements across sustainable governance key areas in analyzed certification schemes..... 48

Figure 20. Distribution of requirements across sustainable governance key areas in each certification scheme..... 49

Figure 21. Distribution of requirements based on alignment with LCA methodology in analyzed certification schemes..... 50

Figure 22. Distribution of requirements based on alignment with LCA methodology in each certification scheme..... 50

Figure 23. Distribution of requirements across qualitative and quantitative in the analyzed certification schemes..... 51

Figure 24. Distribution of requirements across qualitative and quantitative per key area and subarea in the analyzed certification schemes..... 52

Figure 25. Distribution of requirements based on their policy, practice and impact approach in analyzed certification schemes. 53

Figure 26. Distribution of requirements based on policy, practice and impact approaches in each certification scheme..... 54

Figure 27. Distribution of requirements across pillars areas in each monitoring system. 55

Figure 28. Distribution of requirements across pillars in analyzed monitoring systems..... 55

Figure 29. Distribution of requirements across environmental key areas in analyzed monitoring systems..... 56

Figure 30. Distribution of requirements across environmental key areas in each monitoring system. 57

Figure 31. Distribution of requirements across social key areas in analyzed monitoring systems..... 59

Figure 32. Distribution of requirements across social key areas in each monitoring system..... 60

Figure 33. Distribution of requirements across circularity key areas in analyzed monitoring systems..... 61

Figure 34. Distribution of requirements across circularity key areas in each monitoring system..... 61

Figure 35. Distribution of requirements across economic key areas in analyzed monitoring systems..... 62

Figure 36. Distribution of requirements across economic key areas in each monitoring system..... 63

Figure 37. Distribution of requirements across sustainable governance key areas in analyzed monitoring systems. 63

Figure 38. Distribution of requirements across sustainable governance key areas in each monitoring system..... 64

Partners short names

TUB	Technische Universitat Berlin
UNITELMA	Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma
UNI	Ente Italiano di Normazione
AUA	Geoponiko Panepistimion Athinon
USC	Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
NOVA	Institut for politische und Okologische Innovation GMBH
BB	Better Biomass
BAM	Bundesanstalt fuer Materialforschung und Pruefung
RSB	Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association
ISEAL	Iseal Alliance

Abbreviations

BCC	Bio-based carbon content
BSI	British Standards Institution
CAT	Certification Assessment Tool
CFMB	Corporate Fiber & Materials Benchmark
D	Deliverable
EEA	European Environmental Agency
FEFAC	European Feed Manufacturers' Federation
FSC	Forest Stewarship Council
GHG	Greenhouse gas emissions
GMO	Genetically Modified Organisms
GSSI	Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative
IAT	STAR ProBio Integrated Assessment Tool
ITC	International Trade Center
JMS	Joint Monitoring System
iLUC	Indirect land use change
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MS	Monitoring system
OECD	Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
PEFC	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification
SCS	Sustainable certification scheme
SCL	Sustainable certification scheme and label
SCT	STAR ProBio Sustainability Certification Tools
SDGs	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
SL	System level
SSCI	Sustainable Supply Chain Initiative
SSCT	Sustainability Standards Comparison Tool
TC	Total carbon
WWF	World Wide Fund for Nature

Term	Definition
Bio-based products	Products wholly or partly derived from biomass, such as plants, trees or animals (the biomass may have undergone physical, chemical or biological treatment) (BS EN 16751, 2016).
Certification schemes	The system of rules, procedures and management for carrying out the certification, including the standards against which it is certified (Dankers, 2003).
Criteria	The condition to be met in order to operationalize a particular principle (Adapted from Stratmann et al., 2022).
Indicator	A quantitative, qualitative or binary variable that can be measured or described to assess an aspect of a defined criterion (BS EN 16751, 2016).
Indirect land use change (iLUC)	When raw materials are produced on existing agricultural land, the demand for food and feed is maintained, and may lead to someone producing more food and feed elsewhere (Adapted from European Commission, 2012).
Indirect land use change (iLUC) emissions	CO ₂ emissions released into the atmosphere due to indirect land use change (European Commission, 2012).
Label	A certification label is a label or symbol that indicates that compliance with standards has been verified. While the certificate is a form of communication between the seller and the buyer, the label is a form of communication with the end consumer (Dankers, 2003).
Life cycle	All consecutive and/or interlinked stages, including research and development to be carried out, production, trading and its conditions, transport, use and maintenance, throughout the existence of the product or the works or the provision of the service, from raw material acquisition or generation of resources to disposal, clearance and end of service or utilization (Parliament et al., 2018).
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	The compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs and potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle (ISO 14040, 2006).
Monitoring and evaluation system	A continuous process by which an organization draws conclusions about its contribution to intended outcomes and impacts. A monitoring and evaluation system consists of a set of interconnected functions, processes and activities, including the systematic collection of monitoring data on specific indicators

Term	Definition
	and the assessment of impacts (Alliance for Water Stewardship (AWS), 2022).
Non-renewable resources	Minerals, oil, gas and coal. Their use as material and energy sources leads to depletion of the Earth's reserves and they are characterized by the fact that they are not renewed in periods relevant to human beings (European Environment Agency, 2023).
Principle	Core values, objectives, or goals that the system or process being assessed should adhere to (adapted from BS EN 16751:2016)
Qualitative data	Data describing the attributes or properties that an object possesses. The properties are categorized into classes that may be assigned numeric values. However, this has no significance for the data values themselves; the numeric values simply represent attributes of the object concerned (Eurostat, 2014).
Quantitative data	Data express a certain quantity, amount or range. Usually, there are measurement units associated with the data, e.g. meters, as in the case of the height of a person (Eurostat, 2014).
Renewable resources	Renewable resources are resources derived from natural sources that are replenished at a higher rate than they are consumed. Sunlight and wind, for example, are characteristic sources of this category (Adapted from United Nations, 2023).
Secondary raw materials	Secondary raw materials are recycled materials that can be used in manufacturing processes instead of or alongside virgin raw materials (European Parliament, 2023).
Stakeholder	Individual or group that has an interest in any activities or decisions of an organization (UNEP Life Cycle Initiative and Social LC Alliance, 2020).

The bioeconomy holds promise as a sustainable economic model, and certification schemes and labels play a crucial role in guiding bio-based sectors toward sustainability. The STAR4BBS project aims to help ensure that certification schemes and labels are as effective and valuable as they have the potential to be. To this end, the project will develop a monitoring system (see Box 1 on page 12) to assess the performance and robustness of certification schemes and labels (SCLs). The monitoring system under development consists of three levels: system, content and outcome. The system layer addresses governance and operational requirements, the content layer emphasizes environmental, circularity, economic, and social criteria, and the outcome level is designed to estimate the impact of certification systems and labels. The present report presents a first draft of the system and content level indicators that will be proposed to be included in the monitoring system.

The methodology for selection of system level indicators involved a meticulous validation process and a 6-step approach, incorporating 50 good practices from the ISEAL Sustainability Benchmarking Good Practice Guide (ISEAL, 2020). This validation aimed to ensure that the preselected system level elements align with benchmark criteria, further solidifying the credibility and effectiveness of the sustainability certification schemes. The selected categories – *Scheme Management, Standard Setting, Assurance, Traceability and Claims* – each play a distinct role in reinforcing accountability, transparency, and reliability in the pursuit of sustainability goals across diverse industries and value chains.

An in-depth analysis of certification schemes and monitoring systems across the various sectors of the bioeconomy informed the identification of gaps and strengths and designed the basis for the monitoring system indicators. The analysis yielded 3592 requirements, with a great portion addressing social and environmental aspects, particularly workers' rights, ecosystem protection, and the use of hazardous substances. These requirements largely adopt a practical approach, emphasizing the implementation of sustainable practices. While circularity and economic criteria were less prominent, those identified focused preferentially on renewable resource use, resource efficiency, end-of-life product treatments, and profitability.

This report proposes principles, criteria, requirements¹ and guidance notes. They are organized by pillar, key area and subarea, and categorized by sector and life stage to which they relate. Additionally, the indicators previously identified (D3.1- *Report on sustainability indicators for the monitoring system based on Life Cycle Assessment*) and those proposed here after conducting an analysis of circularity indicators are suggested for adoption by certification systems. Future steps include developing an evaluation structure to articulate the monitoring system and assessing the tool with a sample of certification schemes to ensure its effectiveness.

¹ Considering that the analyzed certification schemes and monitoring systems adopted different approaches to categorize the aspects to be evaluated, in this deliverable we use the terms “indicator” and “requirement” interchangeably.

1 Introduction

The bioeconomy is an emerging paradigm on the global stage, representing a potentially sustainable economic model based on the intelligent use of biological resources. According to the European Commission's Joint Research Center, in 2019, the bioeconomy sector in Europe generated more than €657 billion, adding more than €657 billion in value and employing 17.42 million people (European Commission, 2020). If well implemented, the bioeconomy has the potential to reduce dependence on fossil fuels, limit over-exploitation of natural resources, protect the environment and mitigate climate change.

Certification schemes and labels are promising tools for ensuring the sustainability of the bioeconomy. The establishment of robust certification standards is essential to identify bio-based products and processes that meet strict sustainability and circularity criteria. In this way, these tools have the potential to provide consumers, businesses and other stakeholders with a reliable and effective framework to make informed choices and support products and initiatives that are in line with sustainability goals.

Recognizing the important role that certification schemes and labels can play in guiding choices and promoting sustainable and circular practices, the STAR4BBS project was established with the aim to contribute to the refinement and expansion of existing certification standards. To achieve this objective, the project proposes the development of a comprehensive monitoring system designed to assess the reliability, robustness and impact of certifications and labels applicable to bio-based raw materials and bio-based materials and products. This system will be structured across three levels: the system, content, and outcome level. The system level (SL) aims at monitoring broader questions of the schemes and labels and strives to integrate indicators that focus on the characteristics of a certification scheme, including its governance and the development process of standards or other rules related to the certification process. The content layer emphasizes environmental, circularity, economic, and social criteria, and the outcome level is designed to estimate the impact of certification systems and labels.

The robustness of a certification scheme and a certain level of assurance are measure of its trustworthiness, and that certification criteria are indeed met. The robustness in form of the outcomes yielding from SCLs requirements, hinge on several critical parameters. These encompass the governance structure of the certification scheme, the specifications of audit requirements, particularly pertaining to the impartiality and competence of auditors, the approach to risk assessment, including considerations of geographic level and spatial resolution for audits, methodologies for group certification activities, and if applicable, the strategies employed for traceability and tracking. These key elements collectively determine the strength and reliability of a certification scheme, influencing its capacity to install confidence of stakeholders regarding the adherence to established standards (Majer et al. 2023).

A number of SCLs have comparable objectives and common requirements when it comes to design of their management infrastructure (Pelkmans et al. 2013). To establish responsible and effective governance mechanisms for sustainability certification schemes, several critical criteria should be considered. Firstly, there is a need for the

adequate harmonization of policies, regulations, and institutional structures relevant to bioeconomy sectors. This ensures a cohesive and streamlined framework conducive to sustainable practices. Secondly, inclusive consultation processes that engage all relevant sectors of society are essential, emphasizing transparent sharing of information. Such inclusivity fosters diverse perspectives and promotes a well-rounded approach to sustainable practices. Lastly, the implementation of appropriate risk assessment and management, monitoring, and accountability systems is imperative to address challenges effectively and ensure adherence to sustainable bioeconomy standards (FAO, 2021). These governance mechanisms collectively serve as the foundation for fostering a sustainable and responsible bioeconomy.

As indicated in Box 1, within the HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION call, a Joint Monitoring System will be developed by the three sister projects. However, the draft on the content level presented here has been carried out exclusively by the STAR4BBS partners, following specific methodological steps and assumptions. On the other hand, selection of system level indicators included discussions and input from sister project partners, and provided pre-selected requirements will be further refined using stakeholder feedback and other inputs, feeding into the final JMS system level concept.

In a previous deliverable (*D3.1 Report on sustainability indicators for the monitoring system based on Life Cycle Assessment*), sustainability indicators under the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology were identified and presented for potential inclusion in the content level of the monitoring system. In this report, an additional set of indicators is now proposed, after in-depth analysis, to feed both the system and the content level, giving rise to the first draft of the new monitoring system. Moreover, the LCA-based indicators initially presented in Deliverable 3.1 have been integrated into this draft.

Box 1

The **STAR4BBS** project (Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems) is a Coordination and Support action, which addressed the Horizon Europe call HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07: *International and EU sustainability certification schemes for bio-based systems*. Two other projects – **HARMONITOR** (Harmonization and monitoring platform for certification schemes and labels to advance the sustainability of bio-based systems) and **SUSTCERT4BIOBASED** (Sustainability Certification for Biobased Systems), were also awarded to address the same call. The three sister projects work together in the implementation of different joint activities. One of them is the development of a Joint Monitoring System, of which the initial proposal, accepted by the EU officials in June 2023, is included in the Annex of *D4.1 Concept of the monitoring system*.

The goal of the three sister projects working together to develop a Joint Monitoring System (JMS) is to reduce confusion, divergences, and mistrust among stakeholders by creating a harmonized, overarching system. This would bring coherence to the space and clarity for policymakers driving the transition to a bioeconomy in the EU. Working together would allow the projects to build on each other's knowledge and experience, subjecting the JMS to a higher level of scrutiny, and maximizing the effective use of resources. The JMS would streamline stakeholder consultations and reduce fatigue while eliminating competition among the three projects and maximizing the synergies and impacts of the results. The creation of a JMS will require greater coordination, but it is believed to be feasible and worthwhile to work together to provide a more comprehensive and detailed tool, covering a wide range of bio-based sectors and products.

In this deliverable, we will refer to the term “Monitoring System” because it provides recommendations generated within the implementation of STAR4BBS project activities. The deliverable will provide inputs to the development of the Joint Monitoring System. The monitoring system will incorporate a comprehensive set of indicators aimed at gathering crucial information on the effectiveness and robustness of certification schemes and labels. These indicators will be structured into three levels:

I) System Level: These indicators will focus on the characteristics of the certification scheme, including its governance and the development process of standards or labels.

II) Content Level: These indicators will specify the requirements of the certification scheme concerning various EU environmental, social, economic, and circularity priorities and targets. Minimum requirements that all SCLs should adhere to will be defined with a life cycle perspective.

III) Outcome Level: The outcome indicators will measure the impact generated by the certification schemes and labels. They will encompass life-cycle assessment comparison indicators and continual improvement indicators.

In terms of content level indicators, the sustainability indicators presented here differ from those described in the previous deliverable (D3.1) to the extent that they fall outside the LCA methodology. These indicators were finally defined after undergoing a series of steps, including an analysis of sustainability certification schemes (SCS) and monitoring systems (MS), an evaluation of circularity indicators from different sources, and finally the formulation of indicators along with principles, criteria and guidance notes. Moreover, the indicators within system level cover aspects such as certification governance and scheme management, performance, legal compliance, transparency, and traceability. These indicators assess the overall framework and procedures governing the certification schemes, including the rules and procedures for implementation and assessment. Additionally, some systems evaluate the credibility and reliability of certification systems, ensuring adherence to systemic requirements and monitoring the chain of custody. Supply chain management and due diligence obligations are also considered.

2 Methodology

2.1 System level methodology

The overall methodology behind system level indicators selection included 6-step approach, as depicted in Figure 1 below.

Each of the main steps depicted in the above figure was conducted involving a multiphase process, as explained in the section below:

2.1.1 Preparation of a long list of SL elements

For the identification of the SL elements, review of the operational or system requirements from the following sources was undertaken:

- 19 identified monitoring tools (Task 1.5) and the literature review
- Selected SCLs (e.g., RSB)
- Integration of matrix with elements identified by SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project

Figure 1. Graphical representation of methodological approach for SL characteristics selection.

Our approach consisted of firstly looking at all monitoring systems identified in the Task 1.5 of the STAR4BBS project and corresponding deliverable D1.4 as a starting point of identifying lower and higher tier elements for the system level indicators to be included in the JMS. Task 1.5 aimed at understanding the range of different monitoring systems and methodologies, identifying best practices and assessing the appropriateness of the selected systems' methodological approaches for evaluating robustness and effectiveness of certification systems in achieving sustainability goals.

Secondly, we extracted certain SL elements from selected schemes, such as for example RSB. After consultation with sister projects at a subgroup level meeting, we integrated system level elements from D1.2 and D3.1 of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.

2.1.2 Comparing indicators of selected tools

We then proceeded to benchmark all elements from the ITC Standards Map on SL characteristics with the corresponding elements from other tools. The ITC was selected due to considering it as a prospective hosting platform for the JMS, but also because of tool's comprehensiveness, broad range of indicators, consistent updates and adherence to ISEAL's principles for credible benchmarking, making it a valuable choice for ensuring the relevance of the JMS.

During the benchmarking process, we observed high variety in the coverage and classification of system level characteristics among the analysed systems. Thus, we aimed at identifying potential dissimilarities between ITC and other tools, in order to target those areas and subareas not integrated within the ITC tool. Following the results of the benchmarking exercise, we identified the highest comparability and alignment between ITC and two other tools - GSSI and Siegelklarheit, and for this reason we selected those three systems for comparison of lower tier elements of the SL.

2.1.3 Identification and selection of categories for the SL

Based on the identified classification in three selected tools and initial stakeholder input, we categorized system level elements as in the classification structure depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Initially identified categories for the system level

This proposed structure for the system level was validated by STAR4BBS consortium, but also system level subgroup (sister projects) members, during regular system level and core meetings. Upon agreement to align as much as possible all three levels of the JMS categorization, some changes were made. For example, previously added *Subcategories* were excluded from further classification, and instead were integrated into *Categories*. The refinement or restructuring of the SL elements spanned across different phases of the identification and selection process, as predicted at the very beginning of step-by-step approach implementation.

After completing an exercise focused on a specific category, namely Standard Setting (see Results), where we successfully validated our methodological approach, we then shifted our focus to target additional categories and principles. Our selection criteria prioritized those with the most substantial alignment among the selected tools in terms of the elements they encompass. Subsequently, we systematically identified and defined the corresponding indicators stemming from this analysis.

2.1.4 Checking consistency with existing policies and ISEAL guidelines

During all previously mentioned process phases, we checked for consistency with existing ISO (e.g., ISO/IEC 17020, ISO/IEC 17021, ISO/IEC 17065) and national standards and

guidelines (e.g., German Sustainability Code) and policies (e.g., Green Claim Directive) concerning system level indicators, and our method included recurring checking after the first list of the requirements was prepared. In addition, we benchmarked selected elements against the ISEAL Credibility Principles (see Box 2 below) and Annex 3 of *Application of Credibility Principles to each component of monitoring system* of the STAR4BBS deliverable D4.1 *Concept of the monitoring system*.

2.1.5 Stakeholder input

As an important step in elements selection is the stakeholder participation and involvement. To incorporate stakeholders (both internal and external) input in our selection process, we aimed at using online and live events with pre-prepared validation exercises and surveys.

As the refinement and testing of system-level indicators persist beyond the scope of this report, upcoming events, such as the joint cluster co-creation workshop scheduled for December 11th, 2023, will play a pivotal role in gathering additional stakeholder feedback and input. These future engagements are integral to the ongoing improvement of our JMS and will contribute to the iterative indicator development process.

Discussing methodological approach at IFIB side event with project partners and external participants

The first event where the opportunity for stakeholder involvement appeared following selection process, was the IFIB conference in Florence, Italy in September 2023.

The validation exercise for collecting stakeholder feedback entailed presenting an example of a category (*Standard setting*) for which we finalized selection of Principles, Criteria and Indicators. We firstly handed out printed table with categorization and selected characteristics for mention category to the participants (organized in small groups) on a bigger format (poster size). Then, after some minutes, we introduced printed handouts for the groups with the preselection process of Principles for the category Standard setting for all three tools. Here, their task was to include principles

Text Box 2: Using stakeholder input to narrow in on priority indicators for the System Characteristic level of the monitoring system (retrieved from D4.1)

Over the last several months, ISEAL and TUB have led small-scale consultations with stakeholders and with sister project consortium members with the goal of narrowing in on priority system characteristics indicators to include in the monitoring system.

Below are the system characteristics – organized by ISEAL Credibility Principle - that have emerged as priorities from these discussions:

Stakeholder engagement:

- Who manages the standard and who participates in the decision-making
- Stakeholder engagement opportunities, including transparent public consultation on standard and public information on how feedback is used
- Complaints procedure

Transparency:

- Communication of the standard's policies, processes and documents
- Public information on org structure and income / financing structure

Impartiality

- Economic independence from certificate holder and certification body

Reliability

- Type of verification system and audit process (third party verification, audit frequency, what is checked, what qualifies as non-compliance)
- Availability of guidance to support consistent interpretation and implementation
- Documented methodology to assess compliance
- Defined duration of certificate
- Complaints mechanism

Truthfulness

- Claims indicate to what they apply
- Requirements governing use of claims available
- Traceability and chain of custody system

Continual improvement

- How often is standard revised
- Monitoring and evaluation

These topics have been assessed against the ITC Standards Map indicators to determine whether existing criteria and indicators are available on these topics. In year 2 of the project, further consultation with stakeholders, comparison to EU legislative requirements, and an assessment of whether these characteristics are relevant for all types of SCLs will be conducted.

which they consider as worth including besides the three selected principles (in each of the three tools marked with rectangles). The results of the exercise were used for further tuning of the preselection process.

2.1.6 Validation of selected principles, criteria and indicators

As a result of an internal discussion of project partners involved in system characteristics development, we decided to add an extra layer of validation of our preselected SL elements. This was done by using 50 good practices from the ISEAL Sustainability Benchmarking Good Practice Guide (ISEAL 2020). The decision to validate our results with ISEAL practices at this stage, although we applied Credibility Principles at early step in our approach, stemmed from identified need for defining the systems implementation criteria to be included at system level. The aim was to check if the preselected elements contain the benchmark criteria stated in the mentioned Guide, and if not – to implement further criteria from the literature and tools to reflect good practices. There are 8 areas for which benchmark criteria apply to:

- Scheme management
- Standard-Setting
- Assurance
- Group Certification
- Personnel Competence
- Oversight
- Chain of Custody
- Claims and Labels

These benchmark criteria were already outlined by ISEAL in their brochure on introduction to comparing and benchmarking sustainability standards systems (ISEAL 2016). Here they compiled 5 critical elements of credible standards, that coincide with the categories which we selected for system level indicators: Scheme management, Standard-setting, Assurance, Chain of Custody, Claims and labels. The difference lies in our combination of the last two elements (Chain of Custody and Claims and labels) into one category – Traceability and claims.

2.2 Content level methodology

This section describes the methodology used to define the indicators proposed for the content level of the monitoring system under development. In particular, it explains the selection and analysis of certification and monitoring systems (section, 2.2.2 and 2.2.3), the specific search for circularity indicators (section 2.2.4) and the final definition of indicators for the monitoring system (section 2.2.5).

2.2.1 Selection of certification schemes

The certification schemes selected for an in-depth analysis of their criteria, and indicators/ requirements were derived from those identified in Work Package 1 as detailed in Deliverable 1.2 “Report on existing international and EU SCS and labels for feedstock and bio-based materials & products”). From this comprehensive list of 100 certification schemes, a preliminary selection of certifications was conducted based on the following criteria:

1. Exclusion of SCS without global or European coverage, with the assumption that the absence of geographical information indicates a lack of global or European presence.
2. Exclusion of SCS focuses exclusively in the environmental aspect.
3. Exclusion of SCS tailored to organic products.
4. Exclusion of SCS primarily intended for feedstock used in food and/or feed applications.

After this preliminary selection, in which only those SCS meeting the criteria were preselected, the final selection was made by scoring and ranking the remaining certification schemes according to the following criteria:

1. One point per pillar considered. For instance, if the certification included 2 pillars, 2 points were awarded.
2. One point if the certification aligns with ISEAL Credibility principles.

In the event of a tie, the decision was based on analyzing the number of certificates awarded by the scheme under consideration, the coverage of different feedstocks, products, materials, and stages of the value chain within the certification. Preference was given to those with broader commercial and technical scopes. Table 1 shows the SCS and labels selected for the in-depth analysis and Table A1 in the Appendix provides the detailed scoring.

Table 1. List of selected certification schemes for in-depth content analysis.

Selected certification schemes

<i>SCS strongly/or entirely tailored to bio-based feedstocks and/or materials and products</i>
RSB Global Advanced Products Certification
ISCC Plus
OK Biobased
Bio-Based Content
REDcert ²
Green Gold Label
Better Biomass
OK Compost
OK Biodegradable

Selected certification schemes

Cradle to Cradle
Agriculture sector
Rainforest Alliance
Forestry sector, Wood Products and Furniture sector & Paper sector
Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)
Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC)
Aquaculture sector
ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard
Bio-based textile sector
GoodWeave
Green Button
Bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics and rubber sector
COSMOS
Fair Trade specific
Fair for Life
Fairtrade International

2.2.2 Selection of monitoring systems

For the purpose of this report, 12 monitoring systems were analyzed, which were previously identified in Work Package 1 and detailed in Deliverable 1.4 "Report on existing monitoring schemes, with recommendations for new systems." The analyzed monitoring systems are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. List of selected monitoring systems for in-depth content analysis.

Selected monitoring systems
STAR ProBio Sustainability Certification Tools (SCT)
STAR ProBio Integrated Assessment Tool (IAT)
SUMINISTRO
ADVANCEFUEL
Textile Exchange Corporate Fiber & Materials Benchmark (CFMB)
FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool
SSCI Benchmarking and Recognition (Sustainable Supply Chain Initiative)

Selected monitoring systems

WWF Certification Assessment Tool

GSSI Global Benchmark Tool

ITC Standards Maps

GIZ Sustainability Standards Comparison Tool (SSCT) and Siegelklarheit

SME Compass

2.2.3 Data gathering, categorization and content analysis

After the selection of certification schemes and monitoring systems, the content was analyzed by first collecting the information they contained and categorizing it according to various parameters. In the process of data collection, reported principles, criteria, indicators, and requirements were retrieved, along with the classification structure, i.e., categories and subcategories, they provided. The criteria, indicators and requirements were then categorized based on four parameters, which are summarized in Table 3.

Although most certification and monitoring systems report requirements as the last item in their standard hierarchy, some report criteria or indicators and not requirements. For this reason, and for the sake of clarity, the term "requirement" will be used to refer to any of the three during the description of trends found in certification and monitoring systems.

Table 3. Summary of parameters used to categorize criteria, indicators and requirements.

Parameter	Definition	Variables
Classification across areas of concern	This parameter encompasses a hierarchical classification of pillars, key areas, and subareas, as defined in Deliverable 3.1, "Report on sustainability indicators for the monitoring system based on Life Cycle Assessment". This classification system collects the areas of sustainability concern that are the focus of the STAR4BBS project.	Pillars, key areas & subareas , as specified in D3.1 and Table 4 below
Life Cycle Assessment methodology alignment	This parameter determines the extent to which requirements align with the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology.	LCA & non-LCA
Requirement Nature	Parameter that specifies whether the requirement is qualitative or quantitative.	Qualitative & Quantitative
Requirement Type	Parameters that define the orientation of requirements and their evaluation approaches. A distinction can be made between: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Policy-based</i>: indicators/requirements that focus on the company's policies, plans, and related strategies. These requirements assess how well operators adhere to and implement the sustainability policies and plans. 	Policy-based, Practice-based & Impact-based

Parameter
Definition
Variables

- **Practice-based:** indicators/requirements that focus on specific practices and actions that an organization implements in its day-to-day operations. They assess the implementation of sustainable practices in the company's operations.
- **Impact-based:** indicators/requirements that evaluate the concrete results and impacts an organization has in terms of sustainability. They focus on measuring and reducing negative impacts and increasing positive impacts on social, environmental, and economic aspects.

Below is a summary table of the pillars, key areas, and subareas within the projects scope (Table 4).

Table 4. Summary of pillars, key areas and subareas, as defined in D3.1.

Pillar	Key area	Subarea
Environmental	Climate change	GHG emissions
		GHG mitigation
		High carbon stock areas
		Adaptation strategies
	Air	Air quality
	Water	Water quality
		Water depletion
	Soil	Soil quality
		Soil depletion
	Biodiversity	Species diversity
Ecosystems diversity		
Natural resources	Abiotic resources	
	Biotic resources	
	Land use	
	Ecosystem services	
Hazardous substances	Human toxicity	
	Presence of hazardous substances	
Circularity		Durability
		Efficiency
		Closed-loop design
	Production processes	Renewable resources
		Resource-efficiency
		Resource cycling

Pillar	Key area	Subarea
	End-of-life stage	Waste prevention Waste management
	Circular business model	Industrial symbiosis Business model
Social	Workers	Freedom of association and collective bargaining Child labor Forced labor Working conditions Fair salary Mental or physical abuse Equal opportunities/ Discrimination Occupational health and safety Social benefits/social security Employment relationship
	Consumers	Health and safety of end users Feedback mechanisms Transparency Product benefits
	Local community	Migration Health and safety Community engagement Land use rights Respect of indigenous rights Cultural heritage Access to resources Contribution to employment Contribution to local economic development Secure living conditions
	Society	Contribution to economic development Poverty alleviation Food security
	Value chain actors	Fair competition in the market Promoting social responsibility Supplier relationships Respect of intellectual property rights Wealth distribution
	Economic	Profitability

Pillar	Key area	Subarea
	Long-term investment	Feedstock functionality
		Capital investment
		External fundings
		Investment efficiency
		Innovation & Development
	Productivity	Material & energy-related productivity
		Human-related productivity
	Economic risks	Economic & technical risks

Besides the sustainability areas outlined in the D3.1 classification, additional topics were identified among the analyzed certification schemes and monitoring systems. These additional topics, although not included in the scope of the project, were also labeled and categorized as pillars, key areas, and subareas for inclusion in the content analysis. Table 5 provides a summary of these additional pillars, key areas and subareas. It should also be noted that for some requirements they focus on several key areas/subareas and where this was the case, they were categorized as "generic".

Table 5. Summary of additional pillars, key areas, subareas and associated definitions.

Key area	Subarea	Definition
Environmental pillar		
Good practices	Biosafety/Biosecurity	Biosafety and biosecurity aim to safeguard human, animal, and plant health from biological threats. Biosecurity involves preventing the entry of harmful biological agents externally. Biosafety focuses on internal protection within facilities, ensuring safe handling and containment of biological agents.
	Farming	It refers to agricultural practices aiming to promote both productivity and the overall well-being of the ecosystem.
	Infrastructure	It refers to practices on designing, constructing, and managing infrastructure (e.g., roads, skid tracks, bridges) in an environmentally sustainable and safety manner.
Animal welfare	Animal welfare	It involves ensuring humane and ethical treatment of animals throughout their life, covering housing, nutrition, health care, and overall well-being.
Governance	[See Sustainable governance pillar bellow]	[See Sustainable governance pillar bellow]
Social pillar		
Society	Corruption	It considers whether an organization has implemented appropriate measures to prevent corruption and if there is evidence that it has engaged or has been engaged in corruption.

Key area	Subarea	Definition
Sustainable governance pillar		
Management	Sustainable strategy	It refers to goals and commitments, timelines, resource allocations, management plans, policies, enterprise ethics.
	Business management	It refers to business administration, data management (e.g., employers, suppliers, farms geolocation), management capacities of the companies.
	Legal compliance	It refers to whether organizations agree with sustainable laws, regulations, standards, and conventions.
Materiality	Risk and Opportunity	It refers to the assessment of potential risks and damages deliver by the companies, as well as the identification of opportunities
	Stakeholder engagement	It refers to the appropriate information, engagement, communication and respect for stakeholders.
Internal engagement	Capacity building	It refers to the development of knowledge, skills and attitudes in individuals and groups of people.
Customer engagement	Awareness raising	It refers to strategies on customer engagement on sustainable issues.
Leadership	Sustainable leadership	It refers to whether leaders inspire and support action towards a better world.
Reporting	Sustainable reporting	It refers to the practice of measuring, disclosing, and accounting to internal and external stakeholders for organizational performance.
	Assurance	It refers to the level of robustness, accuracy, transparency, and trustworthiness of the information disseminated by the companies.

Based on the previously defined categorization, an in-depth content analysis was conducted to identify prevailing patterns among different certification schemes and monitoring systems in terms of the breadth of sustainable areas addressed and the level of ambition. To this end, the distribution of requirements across different pillars, key areas and subareas was assessed, as well as the prevalence and distribution of different types of requirements (e.g. LCA alignment, qualitative/quantitative nature, and policy, practice or impact approaches).

2.2.4 Analysis of circularity indicators

In addition to the analysis of certification and monitoring systems, further research was conducted on circularity indicators to complement those identified in the SCS and MS. The documents considered for the analysis of circularity indicators were selected according to its relevance on the topic and its availability. In this regard, five main documents were analyzed: the inventory of circularity indicators developed by the OECD, the British Standard BS 8001:2017, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, the Report from the European Environmental Agency 2/2026 and the practice reference UNI/PdR

135:2022. A further description of the framework considered in the documents is described below. While the OECD was used as the main source for the identification of the indicators, the other documents provide guidance and criteria that should be analyzed and considered when evaluating circularity. These documents could help in the effective selection of indicators to cover the required areas of concern related to the circular dimension.

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2021) has developed an inventory of circular economy indicators in 2021, a document containing 474 indicators that have been gathered and developed between 2018 and 2020 to effectively measure the advancements towards the circular economy. These indicators have been selected from the analysis of 29 circular economy studies developed for national, regional and local level. To this end, most of them are more effective when applied to the management of cities or governments than to value chains. So, it is important to critical analyze which of them could be beneficial to introduce into a monitoring system or certification scheme to effectively measure the potentiality of the value chains on the scope of circularity. The inventory has organized the indicators in five areas: environment, governance, economic & business, infrastructure & technology and jobs.

BS 8001:2017 (British Standard Institution, 2017) has been the first guideline on circular economy evaluation, developed by the British Standards Institution (BSI), aiming to help organizations and stakeholders to implement more sustainable and circular practices. It provides the steps to implement the principles of circular economy on organizations aiming to create innovative scheme by encompassing six main principles that should be the guide of the process: systematic thinking (applying an holistic framework to understand how decisions are affecting), innovation, adequate management (measurement of direct and indirect effects over the surrounding environment), collaboration between stakeholders (for example thinking on industrial symbiosis), value optimization (to maximize the value of products along the value chain) and transparency. The rationale behind the selection of this document is because it is the first guideline on assessing circularity, and it has been considered to be helpful on the selection of appropriate indicators to be included in the monitoring system.

Ellen McArthur Foundation (2015) is a framework that aims to evaluate the global challenges regarding climate protection, waste production, biodiversity and pollution, based on three main principles: eliminate waste and pollution, circulate products and materials, and nature regeneration. This framework considers circular economy as a beneficial approach to economic development and the environment, having in mind the regenerative potential of products and process and the opportunities to move forwards the “take-make-waste” model.

The European Environmental Agency (EEA) (2016) has also developed a report to establish possible frameworks and metrics to measure the progress on circular economy, looking to support policy-making and stakeholders on the implementation of circularity. The EEA report has considered that progress monitoring should be focused on the categories of: material input (i.e., how much virgin materials are being used), eco-design (thinking on facilitate products recovery), production, consumption and waste

recycling. This categorization is in line to the one proposed in STAR4BBS projects, so analogies could be detected for the selection of a final list of indicators to measure circularity.

UNI/PdR 135:2022 *Bio-based products - Organization and product application guidelines for environmental and social qualification* is a practice reference designed to provide methodological guidance to manufacturers of bio-based products in assessing the most relevant aspects of the sustainability of bio-based products, with sustainability assessments, both at the organization and product level. The practice provides practical guidance for assessing the environmental, social and circularity aspects of bio-based products throughout their life cycle, including both organizational and product-specific levels. These guidelines are instrumental in conducting benchmarking analyses, implementing eco-design strategies, and achieving sustainability qualifications in line with the objectives outlined in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Apart from the aforementioned documents, also an analysis on available literature on circularity indicators has been developed (i.e. Key Indicators for Monitoring the Circular Economy developed by the *Minister for the Ecological Transition of France* (2021), together with the evaluation of circular economy strategic plans at country and national levels (i.e. Circular Rotterdam: Opportunities for new jobs in a zero waste economy, etc.), in order to gather as much circularity indicators as possible to be afterwards analyzed and selected for its introduction on the monitoring system. By the whole analysis, a total of 704 indicators were identified, which were afterwards selected in accordance with its relevance, operability, robustness & reliability, in addition to avoiding overlaps (more details on these criteria can be found on Deliverable 3.1) and classified with the key areas and subareas defined within the STAR4BBS project (Table 4).

2.2.5 Definition of indicators for the content level of the new monitoring system

From the analysis of certification schemes and monitoring systems and categorization described above indicators for the content level of the monitoring system under development were proposed. They are listed in the Excel database included in Appendix.

For this task, only the criteria, indicators and requirements reported by certification schemes and monitoring systems that were aligned with the pillars, key areas and subareas of the D3.1 classification were considered, as this defines the limits of the project's scope in terms of sustainability areas of concern to be analyzed within the new monitoring system. As a first step, the different issues covered by the requirements/criteria/indicators were identified and the related ones were merged.

The principles, criteria and indicators/ requirements proposed in this report were formulated in accordance with the previously identified and merged sustainability issues. While the criterion poses the question of the specific aspect that we would like to evaluate in the certification scheme, the requirement establishes the conditions that the certification scheme must meet in order to fulfill the criterion. Moreover, guidance notes were provided for each indicator.

For each of the newly established indicators, the sector and value chain to which they apply was defined. In addition, methodological guidance is proposed for consideration by the schemes and labels owners to accordingly improve their standards.

Below is a summary of the various criteria and indicators that will be referred to throughout this report, in order to distinguish between them and their interrelationships (Figure 3):

- 1) Criteria, indicators and requirements identified within certification schemes and monitoring systems. These were the basis to define the indicators of the new monitoring system.
- 2) Indicators and criteria defined for the new monitoring system.
- 3) Indicators identified through the literature that can be potentially adopted by certification schemes. They are also included in the monitoring system under development as additional information.

Figure 3. Summary of the various criteria and indicators/requirements that will be referred to throughout this report. The certification schemes RSB, Better Biomass and the monitoring system FEFAC are included as example. SCS: sustainable certification schemes; MS: monitoring system.

3 Results from the analysis

3.1 System level

Selecting the systems from which we will extract categories and other elements for the SL, preceded their preliminary identification and selection. This led to the initial identification of 7 potential categories (Table 6).

Category
Scheme management
Standard setting
Assurance
Traceability and claims
Compliance
Credibility
Due diligence

Following validity checks and testing exercises from the step 6 of the Methodology, we refined our initial results and selected four main categories for the system level (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Finally selected SL categories.

We integrated previously identified areas (such as Compliance and certain elements of Credibility and Due diligence), that were classified by certain tools as separate categories, under corresponding selected four categories based on their integration within same or similar elements of the screened systems.

To test our methodological approach, as mentioned in the Methodology section, we started with the Standard Setting category. By analyzing the requirements of this category within three selected tools, we ended up with 31 potentially important principles. As this proved to be already quite a comprehensive set of principles to take into account (also due to the high volume of accompanying indicators), we decided to downsize the number of finally selected principles. This was done by qualitative comparison of the tools' principles and their requirements, targeting similarities in coverage. The result was selection of the three most important encompassing principles for the Standard Setting category (see Table 7. Categories and principles of the system level. Table 7).

3.1.1 Selected system level characteristics

The top elements in the system level classification are represented by *categories*. As explained above, 7 categories were initially identified, of which only four were finally selected for further analysis and indicators' selection.

Each of the four selected categories (Scheme management, Standard setting, Assurance, Traceability and claims) contains a number of principles, followed by corresponding one or more criteria, related indicators with guidance notes.

The selected categories and principles are shown in the Table 7, while the whole selection (with accompanying requirements) can be found in the Appendix.

Category	Principle
Scheme management	Scheme objectives
	Scheme legal status
	Stakeholder participation
	Balanced decision-making in governance
	Impartiality
	Transparency
	Complaints
	Compliance
Standard setting	Standard availability
	Standard-setting process
	Standards consultation
Assurance	Assurance system
	Conformity assessment
	Conformity assessment bodies
Traceability and claims	CoC traceability system
	Records for traceability
	Record keeping
	Claims and products labelling policy
	Consequences of misuse of claims
	Minimum percentage input claims

Out of 4 selected categories, we pre-selected 20 principles containing 43 criteria and 43 requirements. The distribution of the number of pre-selected principles per category is shown in Figure 5a, while the distribution of pre-selected criteria and requirements is shown in Figure 5b.

Figure 5. a) distribution of pre-selected principles numbers among categories; b) distribution of criteria and requirements numbers per category.

3.1.2 Categories of the System Level

The operational requirements and set-up of the SCS and labels are shaped and driven by a diverse array of elements, including stakeholder expectations, market demand, the

emergence of potential competitors, policy targets, and the dynamics of internal processes, among other factors (Majer et al., 2023). Among the existing key aspects of development process and system characteristics of a scheme, the four major categories from our analysis proved as the most reflective in terms of overall comprehensiveness and coverage of essential indicators.

3.1.2.1 *Scheme Management*

Scheme Management or Governance and Scheme Management² refers to the set of rules and processes that dictate how a particular scheme or certification program is managed and operated. This category is important in ensuring compliance and verification, and holds important position in maintaining the overall integrity and functionality of a certification scheme.

Balancing the need for robust and transparent procedures for continuous scheme operation, while allowing flexibility for emerging developments, represents a key challenge in scheme management. An essential element within scheme governance and management is the imperative for the scheme owner to maintain economic independence from the certificate holder, ensuring impartiality in decision-making (ITC 2020).

Scheme management encompasses various aspects, including scheme objectives and legal status, impartiality, transparency, internal management procedures, and dispute resolution policies, with existing certification schemes demonstrating diversity in their governance structures.

The outlined principles of scheme management underscore the importance of a sustainability-oriented mission, stakeholder engagement, and transparent communication of impacts and strategies. The scheme owner's commitment to monitoring, evaluation, and adaptive management contributes to the continuous improvement of standards and strategies. Moreover, the disclosure of governance structure and financing information enhances transparency. Stakeholder participation in the governance of the scheme fosters inclusivity and ensures that diverse perspectives are considered (ISEAL 2020). In essence, a well-established and transparent scheme governance framework is fundamental for instilling trust, credibility, and effectiveness in sustainability certification processes, aligning them with overarching sustainability objectives.

3.1.2.2 *Standard Setting*

The standard setting requirements emphasize transparency, inclusivity, adaptability, and effectiveness in the development and maintenance of sustainability standards.

Standard setting encompasses aspects, such as standard availability, continual revision and review of standard processes, complaints mechanisms and consultation with stakeholders, varying from one scheme to another.

Certification schemes should provide comprehensive information on the processes involved in the development and revision of standards. This transparency helps

² At the moment discussing with Consortium and sister projects members whether the second name might be more appropriate for this category.

stakeholders understand how standards are established, ensuring accountability and credibility (ISEAL 2020). The development or revision of standards should involve open consultations, allowing all relevant stakeholders to contribute. This inclusivity ensures that diverse perspectives are considered and contributes to the legitimacy of the standards. A public report back on how issues raised during consultations are addressed further enhances transparency.

Both the standard and consultation drafts should be made freely and publicly available. This ensures that stakeholders, including the public, have access to the evolving standards and can contribute effectively to the consultation process.

The structure of the standard or accompanying guidance should be designed to ensure consistent interpretation. This may involve clearly defined and auditable indicators that facilitate uniform understanding and application of the standards.

Provisions or mechanisms should be in place to ensure that the standard is locally applicable in the regions where it is applied. Recognizing and addressing local context and conditions is essential for the relevance and effectiveness of the standards.

To maintain relevance and responsiveness to evolving challenges, the standard should undergo regular review and revision. The specified time frame (not exceeding five years) ensures that the standards remain up-to-date and adaptable to changes in sustainability expectations and practices.

3.1.2.3 Assurance

Assurance requirements aim to ensure the credibility and reliability of the certification process. Central to this is the transparency of the overall assurance methodology and structure, which must be made publicly available. Accreditation bodies play a pivotal role, required to implement a management system that upholds consistency, competence, and impartiality, adhering to standards such as ISO/IEC 17065, ISO/IEC 17021, or equivalent.

The most important principles identified in this category were: assurance system mechanism (including complaints and assurance requirements), as well as conformity assessment and conformity assessment bodies.

Regular and comprehensive audits are integral to assurance requirements. These audits, conducted at varying intervals based on the sector, involve both office visits and on-site assessments of a representative sample of clients. Stakeholder engagement is integral, providing an opportunity for input to the audit (ISEAL 2020). Publicly available methodologies for determining compliance, including scoring methodologies, enhance transparency. Impartial decision-making on compliance is a fundamental requirement, ensuring objectivity in the certification process.

The assurance framework extends to robust procedures for addressing non-compliances, specifying how clients must rectify issues and outlining the conditions for certificate suspension or revocation. Additionally, a publicly accessible complaints and appeals process ensures transparency and fairness in the resolution of disputes related to certification decisions. Summaries of certification assessment reports are made publicly available, contributing to openness and accountability. Certificates or licenses

define the scope of certification and the duration of validity, while a public list of all certified enterprises promotes transparency. Regular reviews of the assurance program by the scheme owner, with notifications of changes in requirements to assurance bodies and clients, reinforce the commitment to continuous improvement and adaptability in response to evolving sustainability challenges.

Overall, the assurance requirements reinforce the commitment of certification schemes to accountability, impartiality, and the consistent application of standards, instilling confidence in stakeholders and promoting the credibility of sustainability certifications.

3.1.2.4 Traceability and claims

Traceability is an important aspect to consider in the operational requirements of a scheme. Together with the Chain of Custody, it ensures integrity and transparency of certified products throughout the value chain.

This category in our analysis included traceability system for Chain of Custody (CoC) certification, record keeping, and claims and labelling requirements, such as products labelling policies, consequences of misuse of claims, and minimum percentage input claims.

Notably, if a certification scheme involves communicating the origin of products from certified production, chain of custody verification becomes mandatory. This verification extends to all enterprises involved in physically storing products, excluding cases where tamper-proof packaging offers inherent security. The emphasis is on comprehensive assessments, documenting sufficient information to facilitate product tracing and prevent fraud within the supply chain. This meticulous documentation becomes especially critical in maintaining accurate records of product movement, handling, and storage, thereby establishing a clear and verifiable chain of custody (ISEAL 2020).

To fortify the chain of custody, measures are in place to avoid fraud, and exceptions are considered for tamper-proof packaged products. In addition to the outlined requirements, it is imperative to address data security and confidentiality concerns, ensuring the protection of sensitive supply chain information. Integrating technology, regular training for stakeholders, and ongoing audits further contribute to the effectiveness of traceability systems (OECD 2016). These requirements collectively serve to bolster consumer confidence, stakeholder trust, and the overall reliability of certification claims regarding product origin and adherence to sustainability standards across the supply chain.

ISEAL (2021) defines claims as promotional communications about the sustainability attributes of a product or a process. These communications may be business-to-business or business-to-consumer oriented and are made by the system or by its users. Claims can also include the use of logos and/or trust marks.

To ensure adherence and legal compliance, enterprises in the value chain must enter into a legal agreement for the authorized use of claims and labels, reinforcing accountability in conveying accurate information to consumers.

The appropriateness of allowable claims is carefully considered, aligning with the chain of custody models implemented within the certification scheme. Ensuring transparency and verifiability, permissible claims and labels must provide sufficient information for their validity to be easily checked. The schemes should incorporate surveillance strategies, actively monitoring and rectifying instances of misuse of claims and labels. This multifaceted approach not only bolsters the credibility of certified products but also safeguards against misleading or deceptive practices, promoting trust among consumers and stakeholders in the certification process.

3.2 Results and trends from the certification schemes

A total of 2094 requirements were identified from the analysis of certification schemes, with some more topic-specific certifications reporting between 3 and 5 requirements (e.g., OK Biodegradable, OK Compost), while others covered up to a maximum of 297 (Fair for Life).

In terms of pillar distribution, the environmental and social dimensions were the most assessed among the certification standards (44%-41%), followed by sustainable governance (11%) and circularity (4%) (Figure 6). The economic dimension was almost not considered in the certification standards, with a total of 10 requirements (0.5%) reported by ISCC Plus, FSC, REDcert², Rainforest Alliance and PEFC. Some certification schemes focus on a single pillar, namely the Bio-Based Content, OK Biobased, OK Compost and OK Biodegradable certification schemes (Figure 7), which are tailored to circularity strategies (e.g. use of renewable resources, and compostability and biodegradability of materials and products).

Figure 6. Distribution of requirements across pillars in analyzed certification schemes.

COSMOS, Cradle to Cradle and ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard also reported significant coverage of circularity, with 38%, 21% and 15% of their requirements focused on the circularity dimension, respectively (Figure 7). To a lesser extent, ISCC Plus also included circularity requirements, representing 9% of the total. Sustainable governance was not significantly represented in most standards, with the exception of PEFC (56%) and Rainforest Alliance (16%) and, to some extent, RSB, Green Gold Label and FSC (12% each).

The GoodWeave certification stands out for having most of its requirements related to social issues (93% of total requirements), followed by Fair for Life, with 67% of its requirements related to social issues, Green Button (64%), Fairtrade International (59%), Rainforest Alliance (50%), and ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard and ISCC Plus (36% each). The remaining have part of their requirements related to environmental issues, with REDcert², Green Gold Label and Better Biomass having the highest share (86%, 74% and 69%) and GoodWeave having the lowest (5%).

Figure 7. Distribution of requirements across pillars per certification scheme.

3.2.1 Environmental pillar

Looking at the specific issues covered by the standards (Figure 8 and Figure 9), in the environmental pillar, the issues related to hazardous substances are the most addressed, with a total of 265 requirements, followed by biodiversity (235) and natural resources (101) (Figure 8). Within the key area of hazardous substances, the requirements focused mainly on the use, handling and storage of fertilizers, pesticides and other hazardous substances of high concern, as well as the implementation of alternative practices to avoid damage to the environment and human health, such as the use of organic fertilizers, the implementation of integrated pest management and the adoption of green chemistry solutions. Conversely, requirements under human toxicity subarea were rarely identified (Figure 9), with only two certification schemes (e.g., Cradle-to-Cradle and Green Button) requiring operators to conduct a toxicity impact or risk

assessment of their activities. Concerning biodiversity, certification schemes primarily focus on strategies that protect, restore or rehabilitate natural habitats and ecosystems, such as creating buffers, establishing ecological corridors, and protecting legally designated areas (e.g., Natura 2000, IUCN Protected and Conserved Areas). Nonetheless, certification schemes also address biodiversity at a species level, mainly by regulating illegal activities on the land (e.g., hunting, fishing, trapping, collecting), and the use of invasive species and genetically modified organisms (GMOs).

Figure 8. Distribution of requirements across environmental key areas in analyzed certification schemes.

Biotic resources receive significantly more attention from certification schemes than other natural resource subareas, such as abiotic resources, land use, and ecosystem services (Figure 9). The standards emphasize the need of harvesting or collecting biotic resources, including timber, crops and fish stocks, in a sustainable manner that allows sufficient time for the resources to regenerate and continue to be harvested over the long term. Additionally, both RSB and Green Gold Label require sustainable management of land by implementing specific requirements that address the risks of indirect land use change and land use planning (RSB and Green Gold Label, respectively). Only few certifications consider abiotic resources, evaluating the source of minerals resources used (COSMOS) and overseeing energy consumption (Fair for Life, GoodWeave). Furthermore, only RSB, FSC and PEFC consider ecosystem services in their criteria, which require operators to ecologically plan ecosystem services to maintain socio-economic benefits. For instance, forests contribute to air purification, water filtration, and flood and erosion control, in addition to recreational spaces.

Requirements concerning soil (54), water (69), and climate change (55) are also commonly featured in certification standards, though to a lesser extent than hazardous substances, biodiversity, and natural resources. Soil-related requirements emphasize the preservation of soil quality and prevention of erosion, requiring operators to avoid deteriorating soil fertility and structure, and the loss of organic matter and soil biodiversity. Water-related requirements from certification schemes primarily focus on water management to prevent depletion, including keeping water extraction permits up-to-date, implementing sustainable extraction practices, and reducing water

Figure 9. Distribution of requirements across environmental subareas per key area in analyzed certification schemes (only those key areas that have more than one subarea are represented).

consumption. However, they also take into consideration the prevention of water pollution through appropriate practices. Regarding climate change, the evaluation of GHG emissions is by far the most addressed by certifications under this key area, followed by the management of high carbon stock areas.

In addition to the above topics, the review of certification systems gave rise to the category “others”, such as ensuring animal welfare (Figure 8), implementing responsible agricultural practices, complying with biosafety and biosecurity protocols when working with microorganisms (Figure 9), corporate environmental governance, and the pursuit of appropriate infrastructure, such as roads, skid trails and bridges, to facilitate the efficient delivery of goods and services while reducing environmental damage.

It should be emphasized that just because there are fewer requirements for some key areas, such as climate change, does not necessarily mean that they are less important than others with more requirements. In fact, although climate change does not stand out as one of the areas with the most requirements, it is specifically addressed by 12 of the 15 certifications covering the environmental pillar (Figure 10). It was also noted that COSMOS and the ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard do not address climate change, and that the Green Button covers it indirectly as part of a more general requirement on air pollution. Among the other different environmental aspects addressed by the certifications, biodiversity and hazardous substances were the most frequently included in the certification, appearing in 12 and 14 certifications respectively, closely followed by natural resources (11), water (11) and soil (10).

Figure 10. Distribution of requirements across environmental key areas per certification scheme.

3.2.2 Social pillar

The social pillar had the most requirements among the analyzed certification schemes (refer to Figure 6). Workers were the main focus in the standards, with 64% of all requirements directed towards them (see Figure 11). Value chain actors and the local community followed as the most addressed stakeholders, making up 17% and 13% of the requirements, respectively.

Figure 11. Distribution of requirements across social key areas in analyzed certification schemes.

Except for COSMOS, which exclusively focuses on consumers, all certifications address workers (Figure 12). Moreover, the majority of standards require fulfilling specific criteria in relation to the local community, except for REDcert², Green Button, and GoodWeave, which concentrate solely on workers, in addition to the previously mentioned COSMOS and Fairtrade International. Better Biomass leads in local community requirements, with 75% of its social requirements targeted towards the local community.

Value chain actors, the second stakeholder group with the highest total requirements, are encompassed in 7 out of 15 certification schemes covering the social aspect. Fair for Life stands out as the scheme with the most targeted social requirements for this group, at 41%. Additionally, although the overall number of requirements aimed at society is lower, they still appear in 7 certification schemes (see Figure 12). Consumers are the least targeted group, with only COSMOS, Cradle to Cradle, Fair for Life, and FSC having requirements that focus on them. Rather than targeting specific stakeholder groups, Cradle to Cradle prioritizes addressing social needs in a more generic way.

Figure 12. Distribution of requirements across social key areas in each certification scheme.

Occupational health and safety, as well as working conditions, are prevalent topics addressed by certification schemes (Figure 13). The objectives behind the requirements are to facilitate safe working environments with proper lighting, heating, and ventilation mechanisms, and secure working procedures with well-maintained machinery and equipment. The standards impose the requirement for visible safety instructions when dealing with hazardous work and mandate access to protective gear for workers. Emergency preparedness is essential, including the provision of first aid supplies, fire alarms, and safe evacuation procedures. Training is crucial to meet the standards and prevent accidents, and should be conducted regularly to ensure all workers understand emergency procedures. Other requirements include workers' access to drinking water and hygienic sanitary facilities. In addition, all employees must have access to free medical care and regular check-ups. In addition to strictly work spaces, the certification systems also take into account the accommodation conditions that operators provide for workers.

Figure 13. Distribution of requirements across social subareas per key areas in analyzed certification schemes.

Certification schemes also focus on preventing child labor and ensuring special treatment of young workers. Specifically, these schemes require that children are not employed and that those residing on the premises of farms, plantations, or production sites have access to school education. In addition, in case of children involving in family work, standards place strict limits, such as restricting the time spent working and limiting tasks to non-hazardous duties. In addition, specific attention is given to the working conditions of young workers, typically defined as individuals between the ages of 15 and 18. These workers are prohibited from engaging in night work, working in dangerous or strenuous environments, as well as exceeding an 8-hour workday. Furthermore, ensuring equal opportunities and non-discrimination are prevalent issues within certification standards, regardless of gender, age, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, or disability. Furthermore, the requirement for fair and appropriate salaries and the freedom to associate are common themes among the analyzed certification schemes. Direct payment on a fixed and regular schedule is a necessary requirement, while wage deductions are prohibited. Certain certifications, such as Fair for Life, recognize operators who provide transparent and equitable incentives and bonuses to their workforce.

Similarly, certification schemes have requirements to ensure that workers can exercise their rights to assemble and have access to grievance mechanisms. Forced labor, employment relationships, and social benefits and/or social security are also essential issues for standards, for which they have multiple requirements addressing them. Some of these requirements include the prohibition of retaining worker documents, the requirement to have legally binding contracts, and the availability of paid leave for pregnant women or those with illness, disability, or injury. Specific requirements were identified for temporary workers, who must be granted the same working rights as permanent workers by operators. Only a few requirements, mainly from ISCC Plus, Fair for Life, GoodWeave, Green Button, and Fairtrade International, specifically tackle mental and physical abuse. These seek to prevent and prohibit such abuse and also impose discreet compliant mechanisms.

Among requirements targeting value chain actors, the most frequently addressed issues include wealth distribution, promoting social responsibility, and fostering supplier relationships. As for the local community, the issues that more commonly appear in standards are community engagement, respect for indigenous rights, general land use rights, access to resources, and contribution to employment. For instance, Rainforest Alliance requires that certificate holders pay the *Rainforest Alliance Sustainability Differential* to producers based on volumes delivered as an additional payment component aiming to compensate and acknowledge the additional efforts and costs associated with the sustainable production of agricultural products. In addition, FSC has requirements for the protection of traditional knowledge and intellectual property through binding agreements with local communities.

As depicted in Figure 11, consumers and the society at large are the least targeted stakeholder groups. Food security, corruption, and health and safety of end-users are the

main concerns addressed by standards for these stakeholders. In this sense, COSMOS calls on the use natural ingredients that ensure consumer safety or product efficacy, and Green Gold Label specifies that in regions with a Corruption Perception Index (CPI) is below 50 and there inadequate or nonexistent anti-corruption laws, high-risk staff receive specialized training on ethical business practices (e.g., sales, logistics, interaction with local officials).

3.2.3 Circularity pillar

As previously noted, the total number of requirements addressing circularity is relatively low. However, it should be noted that 13 out of the 20 analyzed certification schemes do address circularity aspects, as depicted in Figure 14, albeit the coverage is limited in scope.

Figure 14. Distribution of requirements across circularity key areas in each certification scheme.

Half of the certification schemes focus on a specific circularity issue. For instance, OK Biobased and NEN Bio-based Content address the percentage of bio-based content in their certified products and materials. Meanwhile, OK Compost focuses on whether products and materials can be reused at the end of their useful life through composting. Alongside OK biodegradable, they ensure that the products and materials have a high rate of biodegradability and degradation capacity, while also being environmentally safe in the involved chemical processes. In addition, Fair for Life has few requirements that focus solely on efficient energy use during the production phase. Excluding Fair for Life, the aforementioned certification schemes specifically focused on the circular dimension.

The other seven schemes include standards that cover several circularity aspects. According to RSB, it is necessary to reuse or recycle by-products and waste within production units or transfer them to other sectors that can use them. Rainforest Alliance requires operators to have established waste management procedures to promote recycling. Additionally, this standard highlights the importance of using energy efficiently and reducing reliance on non-renewable sources. Fair for Life also imposes fuel-saving requirements and an increase in renewable energy shares. Similar to RSB, it also requires waste management and reduction strategies, with an emphasis on composting and recycling within the circularity ladder framework. The ASC-MSD Seaweed Standard focuses primarily on reducing waste during the end-of-life stage and promoting energy efficiency through equipment monitoring and gear recovery at the production stage.

Compared to the other certification systems, Cradle to Cradle, COSMOS, and ISCC Plus encompass a wider range of circularity and impose more requirements. Cradle to Cradle include within its standard the need to increase product circularity by innovating in the circular design, such as the capability of products to disassemble into discrete materials for intended recycling pathway, prolonged their durability, an active recovery of products and processing of the materials for their next use. In the production phase, this standard also requires increasing the end-of-use cycling of resources use during the process, as well as decreasing the use of virgin materials. Unlike any other certification analyzed, the Cradle-to-Cradle certification requires operators to develop a plan that identifies the potential partners capable of recovering and processing the product at the end of its initial use, thereby promoting industrial symbiosis.

COSMOS places specific emphasis on the bio-based composition of ingredients and materials used in the manufacture of cosmetic products. Additionally, the standard emphasizes increasing the practice of reducing, reusing, and recycling materials, which includes the use of recycled materials and the provision of easily separable packaging for efficient recycling. It also advocates for the use of renewable materials in packaging and waste recycling at the end of the manufacturing process.

ISCC Plus emphasizes the use of waste and residues as raw materials while considering the waste hierarchy. Moreover, it promotes the utilization of non-intended materials and products as resources during the production phase as one of its main objectives. In addition, the standard highlights the need to distinguish between types of residues and acknowledges the absence of a harmonized definition and classification of waste and residue across the European Union. As can already be intuited based on the aforementioned, the majority of requirements focus on strategies at the design and production phases, with also a relatively notable proportion addressing circularity at the end-of-life stage (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Distribution of requirements across circularity key areas in analyzed certification schemes.

During the design phase of products and materials, certification schemes primarily focus on developing strategies for closing the loop (Figure 16), such as implementing modularity and easy disassembly of products. In the production phase, requirements are allocated among renewable resources, resource-efficiency and resource recycling, with greater emphasis on renewability. Regarding the end-of-life stage, the primary concern is how operators should manage waste to comply with the waste hierarchy.

Figure 16. Number of circularity requirements per circularity subarea and per key area in analyzed certification schemes.

3.2.4 Economic pillar

As shown in Figure 6, the economic aspect receives limited attention from certification schemes, with only a small number of standards having requirements related to this dimension, including REDcert² (2%), ISCC Plus (2%), PEFC (1%), FSC (1%) and Rainforest Alliance (1%). Exploring the specific aspects outlined, the standards primarily focus on the long-term financial investments made by businesses (Figure 17 and Figure 18), especially in formulating plans for ensuring economic viability in the long run and providing adequate resources to support implementation. ISCC plus emphasized the importance of incorporating strategies to mitigate potential risks such as drought, price fluctuations and climate change into the business plan. Additionally, to enhance sustainability, PEFC requires businesses to either invest in research or support research efforts carried out by other organizations.

Figure 17. Distribution of requirements across economic key areas in each certification scheme.

Furthermore, ISCC Plus and Rainforest Alliance both require tracking yields, production costs, and net income as a way to address profitability. Additionally, PEFC encourages exploration of new market opportunities and diversification with new economic activities.

Figure 18. Distribution of requirements across economic key areas in analyzed certification schemes.

3.2.5 Sustainable governance pillar

225 of the total requirements (11% of the total) were multidimensional (Figure 7), focusing on the overall long-term sustainable value creation of companies through a variety of strategies described below. Figure 19 summarizes the sustainable governance key areas covered by the standards analyzed. Management and materiality were by far the most included, being required by all certification schemes except the ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard, which focuses solely on internal engagement within this pillar (Figure 20).

Figure 19. Distribution of requirements across sustainable governance key areas in analyzed certification schemes.

In the management key area, most certifications address the need for management plans and policies that include policies, procedures, strategies, and measures to achieve sustainability goals. Some standards emphasize the need for verifiable targets (e.g., FSC), which should be evaluated frequently to monitor progress toward their achievement. In addition, resource allocation is required to establish, implement, maintain and continually improve the plans.

Materiality refers to the processes used by organizations to identify, prioritize and monitor their specific material issues and to align the interests of the company with those of shareholders, managers, stakeholders and society. In this sense, some certifications require the identification of risks and opportunities for improvement and engaging with stakeholders in a Free, Prior & Informed Consent manner. For example, the PEFC standard requires a regular monitoring and evaluation process of forest resources, including environmental, social and economic aspects, with the results being integrated into the planning process. In addition, Fairtrade International and PEFC include the need for operators to report stakeholder non-compliance, including the nature of the non-compliance, the subsequent actions taken, and the results of the corrective actions.

The ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard, the Rainforest Alliance and PEFC consider internal worker engagement in their standards by requiring operators to provide training and

technical assistance to workers to keep them up to date on business operations, such as good agricultural practices, forestry techniques and waste management strategies. In addition, awareness-raising activities are also part of the internal engagement activities. Additionally, Fair for Life requires companies to organize, participate in or relay campaigns to raise awareness and educate target audiences, such as the general public and other companies, about Fair-Trade issues, and to document these activities.

Figure 20. Distribution of requirements across sustainable governance key areas in each certification scheme.

3.2.6 Trends based on the typology of the requirement.

In addition to examining the specific areas targeted by certification requirements, it is critical to assess their level of exigence. This further assessment is essential for a thorough evaluation of the effectiveness of certification systems as tools for ensuring and improving the overall sustainability of economic activities within the bio-based sectors. To achieve this, the identified requirements have been categorized according to three key criteria: their alignment with the LCA methodology, their qualitative or quantitative nature, and their orientation - whether they are policy-based, practice-based or impact-based. A detailed breakdown of this categorization is provided in Table 3 in Section 2.2.3. As it can be seen in Figure 21, the majority of requirements from certification schemes are not aligned with LCA methodology, i.e. they are not LCA indicators or do not require an impact assessment through the use of LCA indicators.

Figure 21. Distribution of requirements based on alignment with LCA methodology in analyzed certification schemes.

Only five certifications include this type of requirement (Figure 22), with Cradle to Cradle standing out for having a relatively higher proportion of this type of requirement (6% of its total requirements) and a greater variety. This certification framework addresses several environmental areas, including quantifying impacts on human and environmental health, water, soil and climate change. It requires operators to follow the ISO 14040 Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology (with a minimum of cradle-to-gate coverage) and to perform hotspot analysis to identify new improvement strategies. As for the other certifications that refer to the LCA methodology (RSB, REDcert², ISCC Plus and Green Gold Label) (Figure 22), they focus solely on the calculation of GHG emissions and their impact on climate change, requiring compliance with GHG reduction thresholds.

Figure 22. Distribution of requirements based on alignment with LCA methodology in each certification scheme.

Quantitative requirements are the least abundant (Figure 23), being most noticeable in some specific key areas across the different pillars of sustainability (Figure 24). Regarding environmental pillar, the quantification of GHG emissions and targeted reductions is the most recurrent quantitative requirement. Additionally, Rainforest Alliance stands out for including quantitative requirements in relation to pruning and tree recovering practices (e.g., percentage of farmers who prune appropriately according to crop needs, agro-ecological conditions and applicable pruning guidelines).

Figure 23. Distribution of requirements across qualitative and quantitative in the analyzed certification schemes.

Within the circularity pillar, quantitative requirements include thresholds for biodegradability and disintegration capacities, heavy metal concentrations, ecotoxicity levels in compost and share of recycled resources in production processes. In terms of certification standards, Green Button, Cradle to Cradle, Rainforest Alliance and RSB are the ones with the greatest number of quantitative requirements.

From an orientation perspective, most certification schemes focus primarily on sustainable performance through a practice-based approach (Figure 25). This means that operators attain certification by implementing specific practices and strategies in their daily operations. This includes, for instance, the adoption of energy-efficient technologies, the implementation of waste reduction practices, and the integration of practices that contribute to the conservation of biodiversity in operational areas (e.g., buffer zones, ecological corridors, etc.). Moreover, social practices correspond, for instance, to actively participate in local communities, support social initiatives and maintain ethical business practices. Ongoing monitoring and reporting mechanisms are important practices within the sustainable governance to established to track and report progress on a regular basis, reinforcing transparency and accountability in sustainable practices.

Figure 24. Distribution of requirements across qualitative and quantitative per key area and subarea in the analyzed certification schemes.

Figure 25. Distribution of requirements based on their policy, practice and impact approach in analyzed certification schemes.

Less common are requirements based on adherence to and implementation of policies and/or plans, and those that require assessment of impacts and risks across business activities (Figure 25). Policy-based requirements often involve the establishment and implementation of documented sustainability strategies, such as a comprehensive environmental management policy that includes specific targets and procedures for emissions reduction, soil quality management, and integrated pest management. In addition, impact-based requirements, the less common but crucial aspect of certification schemes, are the only ones that appear in certifications tailored to specific aspects of circularity (e.g. OK Compost, OK Biodegradability, OK Biobased and NEN Bio-based Content) (Figure 26), as they focus on ecotoxicity testing of bio-based products, limit their content of heavy metals and other toxic substances, and meet with targets for total carbon (TC) and bio-based carbon content (BCC).

Figure 26. Distribution of requirements based on policy, practice and impact approaches in each certification scheme.

3.3 Results and trends from the monitoring systems

A total of 1498 requirements were identified from the analysis of monitoring systems, with some systems reporting up to 426 requirements (ITC Standards Map), while others between 36 and 78 requirements. All monitoring systems evaluate more than one sustainability pillar, although GSSI Global Benchmark Tool and SSCI Benchmarking and Recognition are focused fundamentally on the environmental and social pillar, respectively (Figure 27).

Figure 27. Distribution of requirements across pillars areas in each monitoring system.

Similar to the results of the content analysis of the certification systems, the social pillar is the one with the most requirements (637) (Figure 28), closely followed by the environmental pillar (608). Circularity and sustainable governance dimensions are similarly represented with only 10% each of the total requirements, while the economic dimension is almost non-existent, with the majority of requirements reported by STAR ProBio SCT.

Figure 28. Distribution of requirements across pillars in analyzed monitoring systems.

3.3.1 Environmental pillar

Following the same trend as certification schemes, hazardous substances (152), biodiversity (131) and natural resources (110) are the top 3 environmental key areas reported by monitoring schemes (Figure 29), in that order. The requirements under the

key area hazardous substances mainly focus on implementing measures to avoid, reduce, and identify greener alternatives to substances of very high concern, as well as the adequate storage and disposal of those substances or other waste. Measures include documenting the application of agrochemicals, monitoring the handling and disposal of agrochemical waste, and ensuring methods that minimize harm to human health, wildlife, plant biodiversity, and water and air quality, for instance, by the prohibition of applying pesticides at specific distances of populated areas or water bodies. For aquaculture, requirements related to the records on veterinary drug and chemical usage, as well as the rationale for their use, were identified. Part of these requirements also relate to the disposal and storage of gray water, the promotion of the reduction of the volume of wastewater and the management and treatment of the quality of wastewater. Only few monitoring systems include requirements regarding the impact of substances on human toxicity, namely, STAR ProBio IAT (Ladu and Morone, 2021) and SCT, ADVANCEFUEL and GIZ SSCT and Siegelklarheit. In addition, all except SUMINISTRO and Textile Exchange CFMB include requirements for hazardous substances, with GIZ SSCT and Siegelklarheit, ITC and FEFAC being the most demanding in this regard (Figure 30).

Figure 29. Distribution of requirements across environmental key areas in analyzed monitoring systems.

Many of the biodiversity-related requirements emphasize the implementation of measures to both promote positive and reduce negative impacts at the ecosystem and habitat levels. These measures focus on the conservation of diverse ecosystems, including wetlands, peatlands, primary forests, protected areas, and highly biodiverse grasslands. This includes ensuring compliance with legislation related to the expansion of biomass production, protecting legal reserves and protected areas, and undertaking rehabilitation and/or restoration of natural habitats. Monitoring systems advocate comprehensive data collection, using technological tools to map areas of ecological importance. Additional requirements specifically address the impact on species diversity, particularly focusing on rare, threatened, or endangered wildlife species, GMO cultivation and the use of non-native species. Among the monitoring systems analyzed, SUMINISTRO is the only one that does not include biodiversity in its requirements.

With respect to natural resources, most requirements identified focus on ensuring the legal and sustainable sourcing of biomass. For example, by requiring operators to take measures to minimize unwanted catches and discards and to prevent overfishing. Another example, this time from the forestry sector, is the requirement to regenerate the tree cover after logging. Only a few requirements (12) cover the sustainable use of fuels and energy (abiotic resources) by specifying the need to monitor and record their use, and another few requirements (5) cover the risk of indirect land use change, urging certification schemes to require information on the agricultural land used for biomass production and the assessment of the risk using tools such as the ILUC risk tool. Regarding natural resources, FEFAC is the only certification scheme that does not provide any requirements referring to this environmental area (Figure 30).

Figure 30. Distribution of requirements across environmental key areas in each monitoring system.

Water is the only key area where all the monitoring schemes have explicit requirements (Figure 30), with a combination of requirements focused on mitigating water scarcity and ensuring water quality. In particular, some monitoring systems require certification schemes to include criteria related to water reuse/recycling or harvesting, criteria related to irrigation efficiency, preventive measures against surface and groundwater contamination, and strategic approaches to managing the transboundary impacts of water pollution.

Climate change requirements are also included in all monitoring systems except the GSSI global benchmark tool, which is a seafood sector initiative focused on sustainable resource management to ensure the long-term health of fish populations and the protection of wild species and ecosystems. Half of the climate change-related requirements relate to greenhouse gas emissions and related measures and strategies to reduce them. There is also a notable proportion requiring the adoption of practices to actively work on carbon sequestration in the soil (e.g., non-tillage, planting cover crops, or intercropping). Only the ITC Standard Map requires certification schemes to include

criteria for climate change adaptation activities and contingency plans or strategies for climate-related hazards, and along with the WWF CAT, are the only ones to require the inclusion of requirements for monitoring and management of high carbon stock areas.

Requirements related to air quality, general good practices, environmental governance and animal welfare are only included in a few monitoring systems. Both ITC Standard Map and STAR ProBio IAT and SCT require the monitoring of air pollution, encompassing impact assessments and the establishment of threshold values. Notably, the GSSI Global Benchmark tool is the primary monitoring system aimed at promoting biosafety and biosecurity through the adoption of best practices. GIZ SSCT and Siegelklarheit, and ITC Standard Map cover various aspects of environmental governance, emphasizing compliance with local, regional and national environmental laws and regulations, and including specific criteria to ensure that up-to-date permits, such as water use rights or land use titles, are in place. In addition, these monitoring tools require the assessment of environmental risks and impacts prior to any significant intensification or expansion of operations and encourage the implementation of proactive mitigation measures. Stakeholder engagement criteria are also defined as an essential part of what certification standards should require facilitating the achievement of environmental goals.

As with the analysis of certification schemes, animal welfare is hardly addressed by the monitoring tools. Only the ITC Standards Map emphasizes the importance of appropriate treatment and welfare of animals and requires certification schemes to address specific aspects such as feeding, water supply, housing, health plans and disease prevention. This framework calls for the inclusion of criteria on protection from predators, humane treatment during procedures such as castration, and the establishment of clear guidelines for transport and slaughter procedures.

3.3.2 Social pillar

Workers again stand out as the stakeholder group most addressed by the identified requirements (413), followed by the local community (118) (Figure 31). Occupational health and safety is the most frequently raised issue among workers, along with providing equal opportunities and decent working conditions, preventing forced and child labor, and promoting fair wages. Preventing mental and physical abuse is the least covered, with only six requirements addressing it.

Occupational health and safety requirements cover a wide range of issues, including the provision of preventive measures, medical care, employee health and safety awareness and training, risk assessments, and incident records. Monitoring systems also require certification schemes to ensure that workers use personal protective equipment and have access to first aid and basic facilities such as water and sanitation. Another recurring theme is the provision of equal opportunities for all employees, which is addressed through a number of criteria, including the establishment of non-discrimination policies, their enforcement, the adoption of corrective action plans, and public commitments to make non-discrimination a priority.

Figure 31. Distribution of requirements across social key areas in analyzed monitoring systems.

Ensuring decent working conditions and safeguarding workers' rights stands as another crucial aspect within the worker stakeholder group. The monitoring tools emphasize adherence to local and national laws, the establishment of reasonable work hours, and the voluntary and compensated nature of overtime hours. Furthermore, these tools address worker grievance procedures, focusing on accessibility, gender balance, and ensuring confidentiality, legitimacy, and protection against retaliation for complainants.

The monitoring tools aim to prevent forced and child labor and to ensure fair wages. They call for a policy against forced, bonded, trafficked or involuntary labor, and require that all workers enter employment voluntarily, with clear communication of terms and conditions. With respect to child labor, certification standards shall establish strict regulations that prohibit productive work for children and ensure that young workers (15-18 years old) are not engaged in hazardous work that jeopardizes their health or education. In addition, monitoring tools evaluate wage-related issues, requiring transparency in compensation details, compliance with legal minimum standards, and regular, timely, and full payment directly to workers. They also address the prohibition of wage deductions except as permitted by law and encourages the provision of clear pay slips. Although a minority of requirements, monitoring tools also assess whether certification schemes include criteria to prohibit any form of abuse, harassment or discrimination, and ensure the right to form or join workers' organizations and the right to social security and insurance coverage.

In terms of sustainable development within the local community, monitoring systems focus on promoting their health and safety, local employment, and economic development. Some requirements also emphasize the need to protect land tenure, access to resources and the rights of indigenous peoples, for example by obtaining free, prior and informed consent before new activities that may affect the rights of local communities. In addition, monitoring tools call for the inclusion of human rights due diligence criteria, particularly in conflict-affected areas. In addition, additional requirements under the social pillar focus on a range of measures to ensure the health and safety of end users, transparency in operations, fair competition in the marketplace, and ethical behavior with suppliers.

Figure 32 shows that the ITC Standards Map and the GIZ SSCT stand out for their holistic approaches, covering a wide range of social issues across different stakeholder groups. Conversely, tools such as STAR ProBio SCT and SSCI Benchmarking excel in specific stakeholder considerations, with a notable focus on workers and value chain actors, respectively. Interestingly, despite workers being a primary target group, one tool, the GSSI Global Benchmarking tool, lacks specific requirements dedicated to them.

Figure 32. Distribution of requirements across social key areas in each monitoring system.

3.3.3 Circularity pillar

Circularity requirements represent a small proportion of the total requirements identified in monitoring systems (Figure 28). The predominant focus is on using renewable materials and energy sources, recycling by-products and resources, and implementing resource efficiency practices across production activities (Figure 33). Additionally, the analyzed monitoring systems require various aspects of product and material circularity, including post-consumer recycled content, amount of packaging, and recyclability of packaging material. Monitoring systems also highlight circular design factors, such as modularity, disassembly for recycling, spare part availability, and the establishment of take-back systems. Furthermore, they promote certification schemes that evaluate product/material quality and durability and encourage the provision of clear consumer guidance on issues such as energy savings, repairability and proper disposal after use. Few other requirements address waste management measures aimed at reducing waste volumes and promoting on-site reuse or recycling of waste. In addition, some of them focus on improving the recovery of by-products and waste streams generated during the production process.

Figure 33. Distribution of requirements across circularity key areas in analyzed monitoring systems.

The Textile Exchange CFMB is the only monitoring tool that includes requirements related to circular business models, such as promoting the substitution of services for the sale of products (Figure 34). It is also the tool with the widest range of circularity requirements, addressing strategies for all stages of the production process. Conversely, ADVANCEFUEL is notable for the compilation of circularity requirements only for production processes. In addition, the ITC Standard Map stands out for having the largest variety of requirements that address circularity in the design phase of products and materials.

Figure 34. Distribution of requirements across circularity key areas in each monitoring system.

3.3.4 Economic pillar

Economic performance is assessed in only 26 out of 1498 requirements, placing the focus on the regular assessment of key economic profitability indicators (Figure 35), such as yields, revenues, and costs, taking corrective actions for improvement. Specific economic metrics are also encouraged to be used, such as manufacturing cost per kilogram of product, discounted cash flow analysis, and external costs are considered for a thorough evaluation. Furthermore, the scheme emphasizes determining the Optimum Plant Capacity and Minimum Feedstock Capacity Requirement for economic efficiency. It also incorporates the Fraction of Revenue for Feedstock Functionality, providing a ratio of product sales value to the unitary value of the crude resource.

In relation to the remaining requirements, they focus on human resources, including the employment of highly qualified personnel and investment in research and development, promoting innovation and expertise within the scheme. Additionally, these requirements emphasize the adoption of measures to enhance resilience and mitigate potential negative impacts from natural hazards, aligning closely with sustainable practices. To ensure financial viability, economic considerations, such as fixed capital investment per kilogram product and discounted payback period, are unequivocally outlined. This involves assessing variations in fixed capital investment at different plant capacities, along with evaluating the ratio of feedstock capacity requirement to feedstock availability in the region.

Figure 35. Distribution of requirements across economic key areas in analyzed monitoring systems.

GIZ SSCT and Siegelklarheit and STAR ProBio IAT only have economic requirements that address profitability (Figure 36), while Textile Exchange CFMB only has requirements that address long-term investment issues. For the other tools that address the economic dimension, they cover a variety of key areas, with STAR ProBio SCT excelling in covering the broader range of key areas.

Figure 36. Distribution of requirements across economic key areas in each monitoring system.

3.3.5 Sustainable governance pillar

Another minority of indicators (126) cover sustainable governance issues and address several key facets that are critical to sustainable management in different sectors. These include strategic sustainability policies, regulatory compliance, and producer commitments and continuous improvement initiatives (Figure 37). Management planning and continuous review processes are also key components of some tools, emphasizing the need for regular assessments, inclusive decision-making, and the integration of economic, social, and environmental considerations.

Figure 37. Distribution of requirements across sustainable governance key areas in analyzed monitoring systems.

All of the monitoring tools that comprise the sustainable governance pillar have requirements in the key area of management (Figure 38). Similar to the circularity dimension, Textile Exchange CFMB stands out for having the most diverse set of requirements that comprehensively cover different governance areas. Notably, this tool is the only one considering management related requirements and is one of the few that addresses internal engagement, as do FEAC, ITC Standards Map and SME Compass.

Figure 38. Distribution of requirements across sustainable governance key areas in each monitoring system.

3.4 Results from other sources

As mentioned above, for each of the key areas and sub-areas defined for the circularity pillar, certain indicators were selected to evaluate, quantitatively or qualitatively, the degree of compliance with specific requirements. The database for the selection of these indicators has been the OECD, following the guidance and recommendations derived from the BS 8001:2017, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, the EEA Report 2/2026 ISSN 1997-8449 and the practice reference UNI/PdR 135:2022, together with some other indicators available on the literature or on alternative action plans at sectorial or national level.

From the total list of indicators, 704, a total of 72 indicators have been identified as possible candidates to be adequate to measure most of the key areas and subareas identified under the circularity pillar (Table 8). It is believed that these indicators could be useful in assessing whether a requirement of a certification scheme is being met by the operator.

Table 8. Preliminary list of circularity indicators.

Key area	Subarea	Indicators
Products and materials design	Generic	Eco-design products and services [number of eco-design products/number of total products, OECD (2021)]
	Durability	Resource duration indicator [longevity indicator, which measures contribution to material retention based on the amount of time a resource is kept in use. The measure is composed of three generic components: initial lifetime, earned refurbished lifetime and earned recycled lifetime, Franklin-Johnson et al. (2016)]
	Closed-loop design	Maximum concentration of compounds on the biodegradability test (Adapted from OK biodegradable)
		Quantity of bio-waste managed by on-site composting [% of total biowaste produced, OECD (2021)]
		Sludge composting indicator (SCI) [quantitative indicator, number, Preisner et al. (2022)]

Key area	Subarea	Indicators
		Percentage of the solid waste that is disposed of in the sanitary landfill [% of total waste, Melbourne-ISO 37120 (ECORYS, 2020)]
		Percentage of the solid waste that is disposed of in an incinerator [% of total waste, Melbourne-ISO 37120 (ECORYS, 2020)]
		Percentage of the solid waste that is burned openly [% of total waste, Melbourne-ISO 37120 (ECORYS, 2020)]
		Percentage of the solid waste that is disposed of in an open dump [% of total waste, Melbourne-ISO 37120 (ECORYS, 2020)]
		Percentage of the solid waste that is recycled [% of total waste, German Resource Efficiency Program II (ECORYS, 2020)]
		Percentage of waste recycled [% of total waste, German Resource Efficiency Program II (ECORYS, 2020)]
		Product-Level Circularity Metric (PCM) [composite indicator, expressed in number, Linder et al. (2017)]
Production processes	Renewable resources	Energy intensity [ton/million EUR, OECD (2021)]
		Energy intensity [TJ, OECD (2021)]
		Final energy intensity [tone of oil equivalent, OECD (2021)]
		Renewable energy [% of renewable energy per total energy required, OECD (2021)]
		Supply of renewable energy [% of total energy required, Gladek et al. (2018)]
		Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption [% of total energy, OECD (2021)]
		Biogenic carbon/total carbon of the bio-based product (EN-16785)
		% natural origin of total = [weight of total product - weight of non-natural origin ingredients) - weight of petrochemical moieties] / weight of all ingredients x 100 (COSMOS)
	Resource-efficiency	Amount of feedstock required/amount of product produced, Material intensity [kg/EUR, OECD (2021)]
		Resource productivity [EUR/kg, OECD (2021)]
		Resource productivity [quantitative indicator, number, Wen and Meng (2015)]
		Total amount of energy/amount of product and/or co-products generated, Energy intensity [TJ, OECD (2021)]
		Total energy intensity [Tone of oil equivalent, OECD (2021)]
		Primary energy intensity [ton/million EUR, OECD (2021)]
		Energy savings [kWh/year, OECD (2021)]
		Amount of materials required/amount of product produced (adapted from OECD (2021))
		Energy saved by energy efficiency programs [TJ, OECD (2021)]
	Resource cycling	Material Circularity Indicator [quantitative, number, Gladek et al. (2018)]
		Close the loop: material circularity [%, WBCSD (2022)]
		Use of recycled raw materials in production processes [% of recycled materials, OECD (2021)]
		Rate of compliance with the obligation to use at least 5% of recycled materials in construction contracts [Rate, OECD (2021)]
		Use of secondary raw materials in production processes [Use rate in %, Monitoring and Statistics Directorate (2017)]
		Mass of waste resources and re-introduced in a production cycle as secondary raw material [mass of waste resources reintroduced, SCREEN project (ECORYS, 2020)]
		Consumption of secondary materials [tones, OECD (2021)]

Key area	Subarea	Indicators
		Recovery ratio of construction waste as material [% of recovery waste, OECD (2021)]
		Cost Recovery Index (CRI) [€/FU, Moral-Pajares et al. (2019)]
		Net revenues from sales of electricity because of energy recovery [EUR/year, Smol and Koneczna (2021)]
		Money saved as a consequence of recovery and reuse of materials [EUR, OECD (2021)]
		CO ₂ avoided as a consequence of recovery and reuse of materials [kg CO ₂ eq. avoided, OECD (2021)]
		Percentage increase in materials recovered (t) and organic recovery (t) [% of materials recovered, OECD (2021)]
		Waste recovery through and inclusive recycling program [amount of waste recovered, OECD (2021)]
	Generic	Electricity from renewable sources in the consumption power plant bars [% of renewable from total energy, OECD (2021)]
		Energy from renewable sources in gross final energy consumption [% of renewable energy from total energy consumption, OECD (2021)]
		Electricity from renewable sources (gross production) [GWh, OECD (2021)]
		Megawatts installed from renewable resources [MW, OECD (2021)]
		Materials from renewable resources [amount of renewable resources/total resources, OECD (2021)]
		Renewable materials use [% of total materials use, Gladek et al. (2018)]
End-of-life stage	Waste prevention	Recycling rate of waste [kg of waste recycled/kg of raw material input, OECD (2021)]
		Waste production per kilogram of product produced. [kg waste/kg product, OECD (2021)]
		Number of bento boxes distributed to reduce disposable packaging [number of units, OECD (2021)]
		Measures in the distribution industry to reduce waste [number of measures, OECD (2021)]
		Zero waste index [numerical indicator, Zaman and Lehman 2013]
		Unsold products recovered for redistribution at the market itself or through nearby community facilities [tones/year, Lukman et al. (2022)]
		Fraction of synergies in the supply chain, compared to the whole supply chain [%, Lukman et al., (2022)]
	Waste management	Wastewater reuse indicator (WRI) [Kayal et al. (2019)]
		Life cycle and cost-benefit studies in waste management [qualitative indicator, if assessment done yes, if not no, OECD (2021)]
		Mapping existing sites for reuse and recycling and needs [yes/no, OECD (2021)]
		Tonnage of waste diverted via repair, reuse, recovery and recycling activities [tons, OECD (2021)]
		Amount of recovered material through an inclusive recycling program [yes/no, OECD (2021)]
		Recycling rate of plastic wasted [%, German Resource Efficiency Program II (ECORYS, 2020)]
		Percentage of waste recycled [% of the total, German Resource Efficiency Program II (ECORYS, 2020)]
		Recycling rate [% per tones of solid waste, CITY keys project (ECORYS, 2020)]
		New types of waste classified as byproducts and with end-of-waste status [number, OECD (2021)]
		Optimize the loop: onsite water circulation [Water volumes per process in the facility, Circular Transition Indicators V3.0: Metrics for business, by business]
		Number of waste disposal sites with a reuse area [number, OECD (2021)]
		Number of places devoted to repair [number, OECD (2021)]

Key area	Subarea	Indicators
		Mapping existing sites for reuse and recycling and needs [yes/no, OECD (2021)]
		Quantity of biowaste managed by onsite composting [% of total biowaste OECD (2021)]
		Reuse waste [kg waste reused/kg waste produced, % of total waste, OECD (2021)]
Circular business model	Industrial symbiosis	Number of industrial symbiosis initiatives [number of initiatives, Monitoring and Statistics Directorate (2017)]

However, it should be noted that using these indicators comes with challenges and risks. For instance, collecting the required data to measure them may exceed an acceptable expenditure. Moreover, data must be collected across the entire value chain, increasing the chances of greenwashing when critical processes are outsourced.

4 Final set of indicators

4.1 System level indicators

The final set of indicators selected for the system level of the new monitoring system is provided in the Excel document separately available as an external Appendix of this report, named System Level Matrix.

These indicators aim to assess the robustness of certification schemes and labels for bio-based materials and products. Each of the 43 indicators consists of the same number of criteria and requirements. The requirements contain integrated guidance notes, and the references of the sources for indicators are included in the separate column.

4.2 Content level indicators

This section presents the final set of indicators formulated for the content level of the monitoring system. These indicators have been defined to assess the sustainability and circularity requirements of certification schemes and labels for bio-based products and materials. As described in the methodology section, each indicator is associated with a criterion, which represents the particular aspect of the certification system being evaluated, while the indicator/ requirement outlines the specific condition that the certification standard must meet in order to satisfy the criterion. The indicators are provided in alignment with the pillars, key areas and sub-areas within the scope of the project, with specific principles guiding the ultimate goal of each component.

The newly established indicators were accompanied by guidance notes, and the specific sector and value chain to which they apply. Additionally, potential examples of indicators were suggested for consideration by certification bodies in their standards. To facilitate accessibility and navigation through the diverse indicators and their corresponding parameters, the Content Level Matrix is provided as an Excel attachment to this report (Appendix- Content Level Matrix).

5 Conclusions

This report presents the preliminary set of indicators designed to cover the system and content levels of the new monitoring system. The final formulation of these indicators was the result of a series of steps, involving the in-depth analysis of certification schemes and monitoring systems, as well as scientific and grey literature, and the selection and merge of key information.

The robustness and assurance of sustainability certification schemes (SCS) and labels are foundational for instilling trust among stakeholders and ensuring the effective adherence to established standards. The key parameters influencing the robustness of these schemes (system level) include governance and managerial structures, assurance requirements, standard setting approaches, and strategies for traceability. The interplay of these elements determines the strength and reliability of certification schemes, influencing their capacity to inspire confidence in stakeholders.

Moreover, the alignment of objectives and common requirements among various sustainability certification schemes and labels, particularly in the design of management infrastructure, highlights the importance of responsible and effective governance mechanisms. Harmonizing policies, engaging diverse sectors through inclusive consultation processes, and implementing robust risk assessment and management systems are crucial aspects.

Regarding the content level, a comprehensive analysis of certification schemes and monitoring systems (involving a total of 19 and 12 certification and monitoring systems, respectively, covering different sectors of the bioeconomy) was conducted on their sustainability and circularity content. The analysis yielded 2094 requirements for certification schemes and a total of 1498 for monitoring systems and revealed that both sets share similar trends across pillars, key areas and subareas, with similar gaps and areas of focus. The analyzed SCS and MS predominantly emphasize the social and environmental pillars, with a specific focus (determined as number of requirements) on workers and local community for the social dimension, and on hazardous substances, biodiversity and natural resources for the environmental pillar. Most reported requirements were qualitative and had a practice approach, meaning that they require operators to implement specific practices to align with the principles and criteria of the standard. Although to a lesser extent, some requirements address circularity and economic aspects, mainly in relation to resource use efficiency, renewable resources, waste management and profitability aspects. In addition, a specific analysis of circularity indicators among relevant documents in the field retrieved 704 indicators, of which a total of 81 were selected as potential indicators to be adopted by certifications bodies in their standards and/or audit processes.

Finally, a comprehensive monitoring system has been proposed to assess the performance and robustness of certification schemes. The newly proposed monitoring system has a holistic approach, including circular and economic dimensions to ensure a fully sustainable development of the bioeconomy.

Moving forward, the next steps include the creation of an evaluation structure that can articulate the defined monitoring system. This evaluation framework will be used to

assess the effectiveness and robustness of certification schemes and labels, identify gaps and opportunities for improvement, and ultimately help ensure that evolving standards are aligned with sustainability and circularity goals.

6 Appendix

6.1 Selection of certification schemes

Table 9. Scoring of certification schemes for the final section.

Certification scheme per sector	Criteria			Additional comments for final decision
	No. pillars	ISEAL	Total	
Agriculture sector				
Rainforest Alliance	3	1	4	
Ifoam Organic Standard	2	0	2	
GlobalG.A.P. Integrated Farm Assurance Certification	2	1	3	
Forestry sector, Wood Products and Furniture sector & Paper sector				
FSC	4	1	5	
PEFC	4	0	4	
Aquaculture sector				
ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard				
Bio-based textile sector				
Global Organic Textile Standard	2	0	2	
Organic Content Standard OCS	1	1	2	
Better Cotton Claims Framework	2	1	3	
Naturtextil IVN certified BEST	2	0	2	
Naturtextil IVN certified	2	0	2	
OEKO-TEX® STeP	3	0	3	
STANDARD 100 by OEKO-TEX®	1	0	1	
LEATHER STANDARD by OEKO-TEX®	1	0	1	
OEKO-TEX® MADE IN GREEN	1	0	1	
OEKO-TEX® STeP	1	0	1	
OEKO-TEX® ECO PASSPORT	1	0	1	
Green Button	3	0	3	Included for its wider range of certified feedstock and products.
GoodWeave International Generic Standard	2	1	3	Included for its wider range of certified products.
Manufacture of bio-based chemicals				
COSMOS	3	0	3	Included for its greater number of licenses granted.
Nature Care Product	3	0	3	
ECOCERT Natural Detergents and Natural Detergents made with Organic	2	0	2	

Certification scheme per sector	Criteria			
A.I.S.E. Charter for Sustainable Cleaning	3	0	3	
Fair Trade Specific	No. pillars	ISEAL	Total	Additional comment for final decision
Fair for Life	4	0	4	Included for its wider range of circularity requirements and higher number of licenses granted.
Fair Trade Certified	2	1	3	
Fairtrade International Trader	3	1	4	Included for its highest number of licenses granted.
WFTO Fair Trade Standard	3	0	3	
Union for Ethical Biotrade sourcing	3	1	4	

6.2 System Level Matrix

- System Level Matrix.xlsx

6.3 Content Level Matrix

- Content Level Matrix.xlsx

7 References

1. Alliance for Water Stewardship (AWS) (2022). AWS Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) Indicator Frameworks.
2. British Standard Institution (bsi) (2017). BS 8001:2017- Framework for implementing the principles of the circular economy in organizations. Guide.
3. Dankers, C. (2003). Environmental and Social Standards, Certification and Labelling for Cash Crops. Rome.
4. ECORYS (2019). Indicators for circular economy (CE) transition in cities - Issues and mapping paper (Version 4). URL https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/system/files/ged/urban_agenda_partnership_on_circular_economy_-_indicators_for_ce_transition_-_issupaper_0.pdf (accessed 20.10.23)
5. Franklin-Johnson, E., Figge, F., Canning, L. (2016). Resource duration as a managerial indicator for Circular Economy performance. Journal of Cleaner Production, 133, 589-598, ISSN 0959-6526. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.05.023
6. Eurostat (2014). Statistics Explained. Glossary. ISSN 2443-8219. URL https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Qualitative_data
7. European Commission (2012). Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC) [WWW Document]. Press Corner. URL https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/MEMO_12_787 (accessed 6.5.23)
8. European Commission (2022). EU Bioeconomy Strategy Progress Report. European Bioeconomy Policy: Stocktaking and future developments. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. doi:10.2777/997651
9. European Environment Agency (EEA) (2016). Circular economy in Europe – developing the knowledge base, Publication Office of the European Union.
10. European Environment Agency (EEA) (2023). Term: non-renewable resource [WWW Document]. EEA Gloss. URL <https://www.eea.europa.eu/help/glossary/eea-glossary/non-renewable-resource> (accessed 04.02.23)
11. European Parliament (2023). Commission 2014-19 New boost for jobs, growth and investment strategy for secondary raw materials strategy for secondary raw materials [WWW Document]. Legis. Train Sched. URL <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-new-boost-for-jobs-growth-and-investment/file-strategy-for-secondary-raw-materials> (accessed 04.02.23)
12. FAO (2021). Aspirational principles and criteria for a sustainable bioeconomy. Rome.
13. Franklin-Johnson, E., Figge, F., Canning, L. (2016). Resource duration as a managerial indicator for Circular Economy performance. J. Clean. Prod., 133, 589-598, ISSN 0959-6526. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.05.023.

14. Federal Ministry of the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety, Consumer Protection (BMUV) (2021). Umwelterklärung 2021 mit integrierter Klimabilanz des Bundesumweltministeriums. URL https://www.bmuv.de/fileadmin/Daten_BMU/Pool/Broschueren/umwelterklaerung_2021_bf.pdf (access 20.10.23)
15. Gladek, E., van Exter, P., Roemers, G., Schlüter, L., de Winter, J., Galle, N., & Dufourmont, J. (2018). Circular Rotterdam-Opportunities for new jobs in a zero waste economy Circular.
16. ISEAL (2016). An introduction to comparing and benchmarking sustainability standards systems. URL <https://www.isealalliance.org/get-involved/resources/brochure-introduction-comparing-and-benchmarking-sustainability-standards>
17. ISEAL (2020). Sustainability Benchmarking Good Practice Guide. Version 1.1.
18. ISEAL (2021). ISEAL Credibility Principles. Version 2.
19. ITC (2020). Standards Map App. Edited by International Trade Centre. URL <https://standardsmap.org/en/identify> (access 13.10.23)
20. Kayal, B., Abu-Ghunmi, D., Abu-Ghunmi, L., Archenti, A., Nicolescu, M., Larkin, C., Corbet, S. (2019). An economic index for measuring firm's circularity: The case of water industry. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance*, 21, 123-129. doi: 10.1016/j.jbef.2018.11.007
21. Kovačič Lukman, R., Brglez, K., Krajnc, D. (2022). A conceptual model for measuring a circular economy of seaports: a case study on Antwerp and Koper ports. *Sustainability*, 14(6), 3467. doi: 10.3390/su14063467
22. Ladu, L., Morone, P. (2021). Holistic approach in the evaluation of the sustainability of bio-based products: An Integrated Assessment Tool. *Sustain. Prod. Consum.*, 28, 911-924. doi: 10.1016/j.spc.2021.07.006
23. Linder, M., Sarasini, S., van Loon, P. (2017). A Metric for Quantifying Product-Level Circularity. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 21, 545-558. doi:10.1111/jiec.12552
24. MacArthur, E. (2015). Circularity indicators: An approach to measuring circularity. *Methodology*, 23.
25. Majer, S., van Dam, J., Fritsche, U.R., Heukels, B., Harris, Z.M., Egnell, G. (2023). Approaches to sustainability compliance and verification for forest biomass. Project report. IEA Bioenergy. Technology Collaboration Programme, Task 45.
26. Monitoring and Statistics Directorate (2017). 10 Key Indicators for Monitoring the Circular Economy, *Statistique Publique*. Minister for the Ecological Transition of France. Paris.

27. Moral Pajares, E., Gallego Valero, L., Román Sánchez, I. (2019). Cost of Urban Wastewater Treatment and Ecotaxes: Evidence from Municipalities in Southern Europe. *Water*, 11, 423. doi: 10.3390/w11030423
28. Norma Española (UNE) (2016). UNE-EN 16751. Bio-based products. Sustainability criteria.
29. Norma Española (UNE) (2006). UNE-EN ISO 14040. Environmental management – Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework.
30. OECD (2016). OECD Due Diligence Guidance for Responsible Supply Chains of Minerals from Conflict-Affected and High-Risk Areas: Third Edition, OECD Publishing, Paris. doi: 10.1787/9789264252479-en
31. OECD (2021). The OECD Inventory of Circular Economy indicators. URL <https://www.oecd.org/cfe/cities/InventoryCircularEconomyIndicators.pdf>
32. Parliament, T.H.E.E., Council, T.H.E., The, O.F., Union, E. (2018). Directive 2014/24/EU of The European Parliament and of The Council of 26 February 2014 on public procurement and repealing Directive 2004/18/EC (Text with EEA relevance). Brussels Comment. EU Public Procure. Law 2014, 65–242. doi: 10.5040/9781509923205.0008
33. Pelkmans, L., Goovaerts, L., Smith, C.T. (Tat), Joudrey, J., Stupak, I., Englund, O., Junginger, M., Goh, C.S., Chum, H., Cowie, A. (2013). Strategic Inter-Task Study: Monitoring Sustainability Certification of Bioenergy Task 4: Recommendations for improvement of sustainability certified markets. URL <https://task40.ieabioenergy.com/wp-content/uploads/sites/29/2013/09/iea-sust-cert-task-4-final2013.pdf>
34. Preisner, M., Smol, M., Horttanainen, M., Deviatkin, I., Havukainen, J., Klavins, M., Ozola-Davidane, R., Kruopienė, J., Szatkowska, B., Appels, L., Houtmeyers, S., Roosalu, K. (2022). Indicators for resource recovery monitoring within the circular economy model implementation in the wastewater sector. *J. Environ. Manage.* 304, 114261. doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.114261
35. Smol, M., Kulczycka, J., Avdiushchenko, A. (2017). Circular economy indicators in relation to eco-innovation in European regions. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 19, 669-678. doi: 10.1007/s10098-016-1323-8
36. Stratmann, M., Ugarte, S., Kähler, F., Gulati, M. (2022). Study of the environmental sustainability requirements of biobased value chains and supply chains for bio-based industry in future EU funded R&I demonstration and flagship projects. Final report.
37. UNEP Life Cycle Initiative, Social LC Alliance (2020). Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020, United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP).
38. UNI (2022). UNI/PdR 135:2022. Bio-based products - Organization and product application guidelines for environmental and social qualification.

39. United Nations (2023). What is renewable energy? Clim. action. URL <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/what-is-renewable-energy> (accessed 4.21.23)
40. Wen, Z., Meng, X. (2015) Quantitative assessment of industrial symbiosis for the promotion of circular economy: A case study of the printed circuit boards industry in China's Suzhou New District. J. Clean. Prod., 90, 211–219. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.03.041
41. World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) (2022). The Circular Transition Indicators v3.0. Metrics for business, by business. URL <https://www.wbcsd.org/Programs/Circular-Economy/Metrics-Measurement/Resources/Circular-Transition-Indicators-v3.0-Metrics-for-business-by-business>
42. Zaman, A. U., Lehmann, S. (2013). The zero waste index: a performance measurement tool for waste management systems in a 'zero waste city'. Journal of cleaner production, 50, 123-132. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.11.041

“ Sustainable bio-based systems via effective certification & labelling ”

Consortium:

Unitelma Sapienza
Università degli Studi di Roma

USC
UNIVERSIDADE DE SANTO CARLOS DE COMPOSTELA

APRE

Funded by
the European Union

www.star4bbs.eu
info@star4bbs.eu

@STAR4BBS

